

D6.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan

skillbill

SKILL TO BOOST INNOVATION & PROFESSIONAL
FULFILLMENT IN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

WHITE RESEARCH (WR)

29/02/2024

Funded by
the European Union

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-02
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
PROJECT NUMBER	101075587
START DAY	1 September 2022
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (updated version)
WORK PACKAGE	6
TASK	6.1
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DATE	February,29 th 2024

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Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	CHANGES	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER
v0.1	2/09/2024	Initial version	White Research (WR)
v0.2	2/23/2024	Consortium review	All partners
v1.0	29/02/2024	Final version	White Research (WR)

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This disclaimer serves to clarify that our calculations and planning were strategic and based on our previous experience, ensuring optimal resource allocation and adherence to project requirements.

SKILLBILL's methodology (GA No. 101075587) for the project's dissemination and communication plan builds on existing expertise, tools and templates developed internally by White Research while also taking into account European Commission guidelines and best practises available in literature. Part of the standard methodology adopted has already been developed and employed in previous research projects where White Research was a beneficiary, such as the INCENTIVE (GA No. 101005330) and POP-Machina (GA No. 821479) projects. Ad hoc and tailored modifications were integrated to the methodology used by SKILLBILL to comply with GA conditions, EU recommendations and project specificities. This report presents the adjusted methodology as it was further developed and applied within SKILLBILL.

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ABBREVIATIONS

BSc	Bachelor of Science
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
Etc.	et cetera
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
MSc	Master of Science
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
RES	Renewable Energy Systems
RFOs	Research Funding Organisations
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SMA	Social Media Account
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

Executive Summary

The purpose of this document is to update, revise and, where appropriate, refine the dissemination and communication strategy that has been and will be followed, as well as to further explain the dissemination and communication activities of the project that have been and will be carried out throughout the duration of the project. In particular, this document is an update of the D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan presented in M4 of the project and defines the strategy, activities and tools that the SKILLBILL project use to disseminate and communicate the project results with the wider public.

It should be noted that effective dissemination and communication activities are of great importance for the SKILLBILL project as they pave the way for the successful use and "take-up" of the project results (EU Master, green portal, policy proposals, etc.) during and after the completion of the project.

The SKILLBILL consortium is therefore committed to continuously revise and refine the dissemination and communication plan and measures to ensure effective dissemination and communication of the project.

The current document has undergone updates based on the consortium's experience gained during the first half of the project, specifically focusing on:

- Dissemination and communication strategy;
- SKILLBILL's promotional video;
- Newsletter;
- Social media accounts (SMAs);
- Internal and External events and conferences;
- Networks and synergies;
- Monitoring and evaluation (updated).

These sections have been revised and adjusted, incorporating insights and lessons learned from the initial stages of the SKILLBILL project.

In particular, the report is structured as follows:

Chapter 1: An **introduction** to the DCP and its goals.

Chapter 2: A brief description of the **SKILLBILL project**.

Chapter 3: The **overview of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy** and its objectives.

Chapter 4: The **target audience** and the respective **key messages** for the identified stakeholders.

Chapter 5: The **tools and channels** used to disseminate and communicate the project's activities and results to the identified targeted stakeholders. (updated)

Chapter 6: This section describes the **roles and responsibilities** of the dissemination manager and the consortium partners for the successful deployment of the D&C strategy.

Chapter 7: The importance of **establishing synergies** with other relevant projects and networks throughout the duration of the project is elaborated in this chapter. (updated)

Chapter 8: This section outlines the **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** that will be used for the **evaluation** of the dissemination efforts and will permit us to adopt the best practices to increase project's impact. In addition, the **reporting process** regarding the dissemination activities is also described. (updated)

Chapter 9: The **timeline** of the four different stages for the implementation of the project's dissemination activities is briefly described in this section.

All partners are expected to actively participate and contribute to the implementation of the dissemination activities, according to the project's dissemination and communication strategy. White Research (WR), as project Dissemination and Communication Manager, leading all respective activities, closely monitors the respective actions described in this document while providing all necessary support.

The DCP, the guidelines and templates, as well as the Annexes (Table 1) included in this report will be subject to updates in line with the project's progress. The experience and lessons learnt throughout the implementation of the project permit us to update and modify the strategy – when needed – to be tailored to the needs of our vision.

Table 1. List of DC plan annexes

Annex	Name	Description
#1	Dissemination and communication guidelines	This is a document, circulated among the consortium, that highlights important aspects of the dissemination and communication activities.
#2	Dissemination and communication reporting template	This is the template that all partners need to update on a monthly basis with information about all the dissemination and communication activities.
#3	Internal conferences and events reporting template	The document that all partners need to fill in after the organisation or their participation in an event.
#4	External conferences and events reporting template	This is a template that partners should send to WR when an interesting relevant event or conference is identified.

During the 1st half of the project, SKILLBILL effectively communicated with a considerable number of stakeholders (1290 by M18). The metrics reveal that more than half of the stakeholders reached during the co-creation and working groups phase belonged to scientific community and industry. The analysis of metrics also highlights the three most successful dissemination channels so far: (i) participation in external events, (ii) sharing results through the SKILLBILL website and social media, and (iii) by publishing the official promotional video. The assessment of engagement activities in this report makes it clear that SKILLBILL's consortium has successfully increased awareness among the targeted stakeholders. Continuous efforts and ongoing monitoring of activities are essential to uphold this momentum and achieve the goals of the DCP in the second half of the project.

1. Introduction

This report presents the updated SKILLBILL's dissemination strategy and establishes the operational framework for the project's partners, as a means to effectively promote the project, communicate its activities and disseminate its outcomes. **The overarching aim of this updated version of the DCP remains the same with D6.1: to promote the project's vision, activities and results to targeted as well as a wide group of stakeholders and in doing so, help SKILLBILL meet its objectives in line with the contractual obligations that the consortium has undertaken with the European Commission.** The ultimate goal is to reach audiences on local, national and European level, as well as, setting up a vibrant community with a well-developed combination of online and offline activities. Furthermore, SKILLBILL's DCP aims to promote and improve the consortium's awareness of SKILLBILL's activities and results by addressing the pre-defined stakeholder target groups. This contributes to the successful implementation of the project, in line with the contractual commitments that the consortium has entered into with the European Commission. It also supports the consortium's efforts to ensure the utilisation and sustainability of the assets developed within the project.

In particular, the DCP offers the answers to some fundamental questions about the communication and dissemination activities of the project (Table2):

Table 2. Summary of DC key-questions

Key questions	SKILLBILL's DCP
What?	Key messages
To Whom?	Target audiences
Who?	Roles & Responsibilities
How?	Communication tools and channels, guidelines, templates
When?	Timeline

Accordingly, this document approaches the fundamental elements for achieving an efficient SKILLBILL dissemination strategy by:

- Bringing in multiple objectives of communication and dissemination activities;
- Defining and assigning to the partners the actions and requirements for the communication and dissemination process, as set in ARTICLE 17 — COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY of Grant Agreement;
- Establishing and addressing key target audiences;
- Displaying the primary information of the project and laying out the main assets;
- Enumerating the tools and communication channels, which will be utilized to reach the target audience, as well as the requisite actions and resources;
- Outlining the internal monitoring, evaluation and reporting of dissemination activities;
- Distributing an indicative schedule of promotional activities that will occur during the life cycle of the project;
- Delivering the applicable guidelines and the corresponding templates for the greatest promotion of the project's results even beyond its closing period.

Communication and dissemination activities is carried throughout the entire lifespan of the project (M1-M36), under the dedicated work package, WP6 – Communication, dissemination, exploitation and social monitoring, in an effort to raise awareness on the project's activities and performance, as an additional feedback mechanism that will better improve consortium's activities. Hence, project's partners continuously emphasize on communicating the messages and findings elicited from SKILLBILL, while engaging stakeholders across a wide selection of both online and physical tools and channels.

It should be underlined that implementing a well-developed and effective dissemination strategy requires the active involvement of all partners, who dedicate time and resources with the intention of raising awareness about the project and successfully interacting with the intended audience.

Overall, the updated DCP will continue to assist partners in designing and implementing their public affairs, communication and engagement activities within the framework of the project. **To this end, it builds upon the evidence of what worked and what did not during the course of the first half of the project and refers to guidelines that can help the project achieve maximum visibility and prepare the ground for the successful market uptake of SKILLBILL's results** (for these guidelines, see Annex 1: SKILLBILL initial dissemination and communication guidelines for consortium partners).

1.1 Updates to the DCP

SKILLBILL's DCP is not static in nature. During the first half of the project, a wide range of actions were planned and performed to promote SKILLBILL and spread its key messages to a large variety of stakeholders across Europe and overseas. The monitoring and evaluation of these targets against benchmarks, as well as the monitoring of the project's progress, allowed us to proceed with some refinements to our initial strategy, in order to make sure that it's relevant to what is happening on the ground and aligned with our project's progress. Overall, our initial strategy has proved to be fit-for-purpose and only minor adjustments were needed. The main adjustments can be found below:

- Dissemination and communication strategy;
- SKILLBILL's promotional video;
- Newsletter;
- Social media accounts (SMAs);
- Internal and External events and conferences;
- Networks and synergies;
- Monitoring and evaluation (updated).

2. About SKILLBILL project

The transition to a low-carbon energy system is a societal challenge not just a technical problem. The complexity of energy policy and the issues that policymakers deal with are not necessarily those that energy consumers face. Moreover, the European Union's targets for tackling climate change are unlikely to be met if the skills and knowledge related to renewable energy sources (RES) among scientists, technicians, and civil society are not well-developed. To achieve this, there is a need for more well-trained and highly educated engineers, installers, and scientists.

SKILLBILL aims to pave the way to different forms of training and education in order to meet new skills requirements in the RES sector as well as engage citizens and stakeholders to get interested or involved in RES regardless of the initial level of education, their working position and their gender.

The presence of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), communication and scientific experts will involve the four core components of the innovation system (Quadruple Helix Model: academia, industry, government, society) in a dedicated **Green Portal**, to improve social acceptance and encourage social innovation in bi-directional interactions:

- Providing a **comprehensive and effective information on RES technologies** to a large target audience;
- Ensuring that the next generation technology **meets citizens' needs and expectation together** with the environmental requirement;
- Encouraging **women to exploit their full potential in STEM**;
- **Maximizing the technicians' skills tutoring** and driving the students through their course of **study to maximise their talents**.

Taking into consideration that differences in employment and training opportunities often translate into further social challenges such as social exclusion and an unequal access to higher education, SKILLBILL aims at meeting new skills requirements for greater economic stability and equity.

The activities of **Vocational and Educational training** and the **European Master**, taking place in the framework of SKILLBILL, will facilitate the participation of both - adults returning to study and youngsters looking for opportunities in science. Flexible benefits, such as part-time, modular or evening courses, or distance-learning provision, making use of the enabling power of new technologies such as Virtual Reality and Enhanced Reality will help engage various stakeholders in RES education and training.

Thus, SKILLBILL's main objectives are:

- Steer the development of a greener, more effective and pervasive RES education;
- Launch the point of reference for qualitative information on RES and promote and accelerate the development of sustainable solutions (Green Portal);
- Develop an advanced permanent education program on RES at European level;
- Develop a technical practical permanent Vocational Education Training program on RES;
- Reduce gender gap in STEM;
- Increase awareness, reducing the lack of information, bad quality material and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy, therefore improving inclusiveness on RES.

3. Dissemination and communication strategy

3.1 Overview

SKILLBILL's DCP describes the overall D&C strategy of the project concerning the dissemination and communication of the outcomes. The strategy was carefully designed and tailored to the approach of the project aiming to maximise its impact, transfer knowledge and the results to the targeted stakeholders, as well as to communicate its concept to wider audiences. This strategy establishes clear guidelines for all dissemination activities that will take place throughout the project, including all operational dissemination elements. These elements are illustrated in the figure below (Figure1)¹:

Figure 1. Overview of the SKILLBILL dissemination and communication strategy

This section presents the overview of the D&C strategy and outlines the structure of the DCP. First of all, the first sub-section presents the **objectives of the DCP** which are used to monitor the successful implementation of the strategy. The second sub-section defines **the target audience** to whom we disseminate the project's results. The next sub-section presents the **key messages** for each one of the targeted stakeholders, as well as the **core visions and assets**. A dedicated sub-section of the strategy, the fourth, focuses on the **means, channels, and tools that are used to reach the identified stakeholders**. In the following sub-sections, the allocation of **roles and responsibilities** and the timelines for the dissemination strategy will be clearly elaborated to ensure the smooth and effective implementation of the DCP.

Throughout the duration of the project, special attention is given to the **cooperation with other relevant projects** at national and European level. Although there is a dedicated task (T6.5) for establishing synergies with other relevant projects and networks, the document presents a short

¹ Inspired by Fig.1 of: Gaillard, M., and N. Germain, "Deliverable 9.2 – Dissemination and communication plan", DTOceanPlus, France Energies Marines, 10 December 2018, p.10

introduction regarding the initial plan. Lastly, the final chapter presents a robust framework for the assessment of the strategy along with a timeline for the dissemination and communication steps.

Aiming to ensure the successful dissemination and communication of results, the DCP constitutes a guidelines document that presents the tools and actions which navigates the consortium partners to successfully engage the targeted stakeholders.

Of course, the DCP should not be seen as a static document, but as a dynamic, flexible strategy that is reviewed and - if necessary - updated during the life cycle of the project, just as this document is.

3.2 Objectives of the DCP

The first version of SKILLBILL DCP outlined a comprehensive dissemination strategy, which takes into account numerous important factors and spans the whole project period. It therefore serves as a horizontal document that is linked to every section of the project workplan and its associated activities.

Overall, communication, promoting the project's action and results, and dissemination actions, making project's results public, offering high visibility to events and activities, paving the way for the effective promotion of the project's vision, its actual unfolding and its results among a wide range of stakeholders. In that way, the updated DCP keeps assisting the success of various work packages, as well as the exploitation of SKILLBILL's results, while supporting the project's impact through the exploitation of knowledge generated by the project. Thus, DCP is strategically essential since it outlines the expectations in relation to each partner's involvement in the dissemination process, as well as the required dissemination tasks that should be carried out throughout the project.

In general, the D&C of SKILLBILL aims to accomplish a number of high-level objectives:

- Present the project's aim, vision, activities and events to a wider audience;
- Promote awareness raising among stakeholder groups;
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities;
- Engage stakeholders through a series of relevant activities, events and conferences;
- Ensure that the key messages are communicated to its target audiences;
- Ensure the exploitation of the project's outcomes (such as the SKILLBILL Green Portal, Joint Stakeholder Initiative, European Master program, Vocational Education and Training program, Reduce Gender Gap);
- Encourage the replication of the SKILLBILL methodology;
- Introduce scientific concepts in an easy to grasp way to stakeholders and citizens;
- Plan, organise, run, monitor and fine-tune the project's dissemination activities and events;
- Establish and sustain synergies with other relevant national and European projects and networks;
- Disseminate the project's lessons and outcomes in an open and transparent way;
- Establish an active community exchanging ideas and knowledge in topics relevant to the project.

To ensure the achievement of the above objectives, the dissemination and communication strategy focuses on the implementation of a realistic action plan with the goal of involving as many target audiences as possible, while also providing the option of flexible solutions where necessary. The

existence of a well-defined methodology that refers to **what** is wanted to be disseminated (vision, news, achievements, results), to **whom** (stakeholders, target groups), by **what means** (strategies, tools, channels), and **when** to disseminate are key elements of a successful D&C plan.

Taking this into account, the following steps for project dissemination and communication emerged while building the first version of project's DC strategy:

- Determine the project's goals, as well as the communication channels and tools required for maximum visibility and promotion;
- Identify the key messages and project's assets;
- Link each communication channel to the appropriate target group and define the tools and methods to be used in project dissemination;
- Define each partner's roles and responsibilities so that they actively participate and manage the project's dissemination and communication activities;
- Monitor key dissemination indicators and make appropriate changes where necessary;
- Determine steps during the project's dissemination and communication activities and monitor the actions' consistency with the overall timeline.

4. Target audiences and key messages

4.1 SKILLBILL's target audiences

The primary goal of dissemination and communication activities is to circulate information about the project's vision, its results, and solutions, thereby maximizing the project's impact. As a result, it is critical to define the target groups to whom the D&C plan is directed.

The main stakeholder groups, expected to be reached over the project's duration, are illustrated in Figure 2. In terms of the relevance of their field of action, these are deemed to be the most appropriate for SKILLBILL. As seen, these target groups represent a diverse range of professions, as well as distinct interactions with the sustainable energy sector and renewable energy sources.

Figure 2. SKILLBILL target audiences

Particularly, SKILLBILL aims to engage a wide variety of stakeholders with different backgrounds and experiences. In particular the project's primary targets are:

1. **Academic community** (professors, BSc & MSc students, PhD candidates, etc.)
2. **Scientific community** (RES experts, engineers, ecologists, STEM experts, etc.)
3. **Policy Makers** (local / national / EU policy makers in energy, environment, climate change etc.)
4. **Energy authorities and associations** (national energy associations, sector organisations e.g. bioenergy / hydrogen / solar, regulatory authorities etc.)
5. **Civil society** (consumers, local community, general public etc.)
6. **NGOs** (citizen's initiatives, national and EU level climate and energy organisations etc)
7. **RES Industry**
8. **Technology providers**

9. SMEs

10. **Vulnerable groups** (women of all ages, profession and educational level, elderly people, people of low socioeconomic status)

During the project’s lifespan, it remains important to classify them to better prioritise and fine-tune our engagement efforts. To this aim, the Stakeholders Classification Model² will be used in order to classify each targeted stakeholder group based on the following parameters:

- The extent of a stakeholder’s power/authority;
- The stakeholder’s interest regarding the outcomes of the project;
- The extent of the stakeholder’s active involvement in the project;
- The level of stakeholder’s influence over the project planning and/or outcomes.

The stakeholder groups and subgroups will be extended also during the activities of WP2 | T2.1: “Stakeholder community mapping and user research to better appreciate current training needs and skilling practices”.

The classification of the targeted stakeholders’ groups will be used to tailor the communicated messages and adopt the most suitable tools and dissemination channels for each one of the groups. The following figure (Figure 3) depicts the parameters and how they define different types of stakeholder engagement:

Figure 3. Stakeholder mapping and types of stakeholder engagement

The D&C strategy aims to reach the above-mentioned identified audiences which were further categorised into the broader SKILLBILL stakeholder groups. An indicative list of identified stakeholders per target group is provided below:

² Emerson Wagner Mainardes, Helena Alves, Mário Raposo, (2012). “A model for stakeholder classification and stakeholder relationships”, Management Decision, Vol. 50 Issue: 10, pp. 1861-1879.

Table 3. SKILLBILL target audience categories

Target Group	Short description	Sub-categories
Scientific community	Network of interacting scientists who conduct research in the fields of sustainable energy, renewable energy sources, new materials, engineering, business models etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Professors • Research Organizations • Educational Institutes • Experts and individual researchers
RES Industry	Industries and / or industry associations operating in the field of renewable energy at a European or global level.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&D units in private companies • Experts and individual researchers • RES industry support organisation • Solar Power Industry • Wind Energy Industry • Geothermal Energy Industry • Biomass Energy Industry • Research Companies • Nanotechnology Industry
SMEs	Small-medium enterprises in the field of renewable energy at a European or global level.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workers • Engineers • Field experts • RES designers
Energy authorities and associations	National (and European) associations, local and regional authorities that play a role in promoting sustainable energy and renewable energy sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International policy makers and public authorities • Regulatory authorities • EU decision makers • National public authorities
Civil society	Individuals and organisations who are interested in enhancing their knowledge on sustainable energy and renewable energy sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Civil Society Organisation
Organizations and Institutions	Organisations (governmental and non-governmental) active in the areas of environmental conservation and preventing degradation of natural resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Organizations • NGOs • Bioenergy and sustainable energy associations • Financial and Governmental Institutions
Relevant EU initiatives	Both ongoing and completed European projects which focus on disciplines related to SKILLBILL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizon Europe • Horizon 2020 projects • Other EU and national funded projects (e.g. Interreg, Erasmus+)

4.2 SKILLBILL's key-messages

The main messages communicated to the target groups are an important aspect for an effective dissemination and communication plan. These messages must be consistent with the project's concept and vision, but they must also be tailored to the needs of the target audiences. This is also the primary reason why **different stakeholder groups receive different messages**. As mentioned before, the identified target groups were further enriched during T2.1 activities (*completed in M9 – D2.1*). For the same reason, the messages delivered during SKILLBILL are subject to change and constantly optimized based on experience and monitoring of dissemination results.

Table 4. SKILLBILL's target audience, needs and messages

Target Group	Need	Key message
Academic community (professors, BSc & MSc students, PhD candidates, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To keep up with science and technology trends; ○ To meet and adopt novel education - training practices in RES; ○ To identify educational gaps on properly engaging stakeholders in RES. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Promote best-practices on RES education and training; ✓ Inform academic community on novel technologies and trends in renewable energy sector; ✓ Fill the gaps in education and training on RES; ✓ Offer skills to strengthen capabilities; ✓ Shed light to best practices on RES education & training.
Scientific community (RES experts, engineers, ecologists, STEM experts, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To explore new research fields; ○ To keep up with research and development of new RES technologies; ○ To be introduced in sciences related to the RES field. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Bring together scientists from different fields related to RES; ✓ Promote novel research and development results; ✓ Promote knowledge transfer and innovation at academic level; ✓ Exchange feedback among the scientific community to address and solve scientific & technological challenges.
Policy Makers (local / national / EU policy makers in energy, environment, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To understand the current landscape of RES sector and how can they be a part of sector's development; ○ To monitor the progress in the field of RES technologies and support education – training on the sector; ○ To have actual data and consistent information on the current developments in the renewable energy field. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Promote the development of legal and standard (regulatory framework) aspects on RES; ✓ Get feedback from energy authorities and associations on current state in renewable energy fields and stakeholders' engagement; ✓ Provide clear and consistent information on RES.
Energy authorities and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To be in touch with RES stakeholders; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Bring together industry, civil society, academia and research

<p>associations (national energy associations, bioenergy associations, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To follow trends in renewable energy sector; ○ To stay informed about stakeholders' involvement in RES. 	<p>with energy authorities and associations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Promote new educational – training practices and novel technologies.
<p>Civil society & General Public (consumers, sellers, citizens' initiatives, local communities, NGO's etc)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To reach higher levels of awareness and gain knowledge on renewable energy sector; ○ To build trust for RES technologies application in everyday life; ○ To be well educated and trained on sustainable energy and “circularity-by-design” on RES; ○ To stay updated on the latest trends in RES sector; ○ To have access to results regarding the benefits from RES use; ○ To introduce citizens to RES education and training; ○ To engage and inform more citizens about sustainable and renewable energy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Promote project assets to capture public attention on their potential ✓ Underline direct benefits for society and environment; ✓ Provide clear and consistent information on RES; ✓ Explain the positive impact from the adoption of RES use for the industry, the local community and the environment; ✓ Integrate education and training best practices derived from the project into civil society; ✓ Offer skills to strengthen capabilities; ✓ Shed light to best practices on RES education & training.
<p>RES Industry</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To meet new technologies on RES; ○ To train employees on RES; ○ To be further involved in RES market; ○ To be in touch with RES scientists and follow research trends. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Bring together industry, civil society, academia and research with energy authorities and associations; ✓ Integrate education and training best practices derived from the project into civil society; ✓ Inform on novel technologies and trends in the renewable energy sector.
<p>Technology providers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To be more involved in RES market; ○ To be educated – trained on trends in renewable energy field; ○ To meet new technologies; ○ To be skilled or reskilled to face market requests or new RES Policies; ○ To fulfil the demand of citizens or industries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Promote new educational – training practices and novel technologies; ✓ Promote novel research and development results; ✓ Bring together industry, civil society, academia and research with energy.
<p>SMEs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To meet new RES technologies; ○ To effectively monitor trends in RES market; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Bring together industry, civil society, academia and research with energy authorities and associations;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To educate and train employees on RES; ○ To adopt activities of novel research and development on RES. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Integrate education and training best practices derived from the project into civil society; ✓ Inform on novel technologies and trends in renewable energy sector;
<p>Women in STEM</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To bridge the gender gap that keeps women away from RES and STEM; ○ To be educated – trained in RES sector and STEM field; ○ To open new job opportunities in the renewable energy field. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Promote public attention on women’s involvement in renewable energy sector; ✓ Boost-up and foster women’s involvement in RES; ✓ Underline direct benefits for society and environment from bridging the gender gap; ✓ Provide clear and consistent information on RES; ✓ Offer skills to strengthen capabilities; ✓ Shed light to best practices on RES education & training.

4.3 Gender Issues

The dissemination strategy of SKILLBILL targets all genders equally. Gender-neutral language is used in all communication and dissemination materials of the project throughout its implementation.

Promoting STEM pathways among women is one of the main focuses of the SKILLBILL project. To achieve this, inclusiveness and precise gender equality stand at the core of the SKILLBILL project. The consortium addresses sex, gender, and equality issues early in the proposal phase. During the implementation stage, reducing the gender gap in STEM remains a primary focus of the SKILLBILL project. The consortium ensures respect for gender equality and prevents discrimination based on a person's gender during the project’s activities. Identification and elimination of gender biases, stereotypes, and discrimination in the field are prioritized. SKILLBILL specifically targets the gender gap and aims to eliminate it through various activities, tools, and appropriate language. White Research, particularly in the Communication and Dissemination strategy, pays close attention to this issue to ensure adherence to these principles.

Regarding training activities within SKILLBILL, White Research ensures that training and educational activities are promoted to encourage the involvement of women RES scientists and engineers in the future industrial landscape.

To monitor progress in this area, the engagement of women in the project’s events, as well as via social media, is being tracked.

5. Communication and Dissemination tools and channels

SKILLBILL's DCP deploys multiple tools and channels to ensure that activities and outcomes reach a wide array of stakeholders and contribute to promoting effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and labels. Here is an overview of the various tools, channels, and planned dissemination activities, demonstrating HOW the D&C strategy is implemented: (Figure 4).

Figure 4. SKILLBILL's communication activities

The SKILLBILL promotional material and graphical identity includes:

- Project's logo
- Project's visual and graphical identity
- Trifold leaflet
- Poster
- Presentation template
- Letterheads
- Promotional video
- Ad hoc promotional material (tailored to the project's activities and needs – e.g. project banner)

The SKILLBILL online presence includes:

- Web portal
- Bi-annual Newsletter
- Facebook page
- Twitter account
- LinkedIn profile
- YouTube channel

The SKILLBILL events include:

- Engagement events
- Participation in external events and conferences as SKILLBILL representatives
- Presentation of SKILLBILL in external events and conferences
- Final dissemination event

- Co-organisation and participation in events with projects we have established synergies with
- Organisation of project trainings, technical & policy workshops and webinars

The SKILLBILL publications include:

- Project’s deliverables
- Scientific publications
- Other publications in different media (e.g., articles, press releases etc.)

The SKILLBILL dissemination network:

- Synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives
- Networking activities with other EU funded projects from previous H2020 and / or Horizon Europe calls

Specific tools and channels are used for communicating and disseminating the project’s activities and outcomes to the identified target groups. Below are presented in a summarized way:

Table 5. Tools and channels used for the identified target groups

<i>Target Groups</i>	<i>Tools and channels</i>
Academic community	External events, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, web portal, scientific publications, project’s reports, synergies with other projects, targeted emails, project partner’s websites
Scientific community	External events, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, web portal, scientific publications, project’s reports, synergies with other projects, project partner’s websites
Policy Makers	Project events, external events, workshops, SMAs, leaflet, poster, project’s reports, personal contacts
Energy authorities and associations	Project events, external events, workshops, SMAs, leaflet, poster, project’s reports, personal contacts
Civil society	External events, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, Green Portal, web portal, project partner’s websites
General public	External events, SMAs, Green Portal, web-portal, Newsletter, project’s reports, synergies with other projects, leaflet, poster, project partner’s websites
RES Industry	Project events, external events, workshops, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, Green Portal, web portal

Technology providers	Project events, workshops, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, web portal, project's reports
SME's	External events, workshops, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, Green Portal, web portal
Women of all ages, profession and educational level	External events, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, Green Portal, web portal, scientific publications, project's reports, synergies with other projects, personal contacts to female organisations/associations in the respective countries

5.1 Promotional material

The promotional material of SKILLBILL was prepared during the early stages of the project. White Research (WR) was responsible for the graphic design and the content, while the consortium partners offered feedback throughout the development process. **The material is freely available to the public through the project's website (online for download) and for partners to print it when needed.** The material is used during physical activities (including external and internal project's events) to attract and engage relevant stakeholders and give more information on the project's mission and objectives.

All the promotional material was designed based on the project's unique identity that is presented in the following paragraph.

5.1.1 SKILLBILL's Logo

The project logo, in conjunction with the general graphic elements and the aesthetic concept, is what distinguishes the project and serves as the foundation for the further development of the entire promotion package (e.g. leaflets, posters, infographics, newsletters, deliverables, social media, web-portal, publications, publicity for internal and external events, etc.) that is used in all dissemination and communications activities.

During M1, the project partners were invited to participate in an online voting during kick-off meeting for the project's logo, where a variety of logo options were presented to them. Figure 5 illustrates the logo which received the majority of the votes.

Figure 5. SKILLBILL's logo

The design of the logo represents RES, education, nature, sustainability and gender balance. The white network that appears inside the green leaf represents the stakeholder community engagement. The person with the hat touching the network represents education and knowledge sharing. The circle with the arrow and the plus icon represents gender equality and the wind turbine in the centre symbolizes renewable energy sources.

The colour palette (Figure 6) combines shades of greens which are basic colours for sustainability, green solutions and innovation.

Figure 6. The color palette of SKILLBILL's Logo

The SKILLBILL logo should be visible to all the communication material produced in the framework of the project (presentation, deliverables etc.). Similarly, the EU funding should be properly acknowledged, and the EU emblem should also be properly depicted in all communication material.

Figure 7. The emblem of the European Union

The EU flag is always accompanied by the following statement:

“Funded by the European Union”.

“Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

5.1.2 SKILLBILL’s leaflet & poster

Leaflets and posters are another basic tool for the correct implementation of dissemination & communication actions. The use of these elements highlights both the project's content and goals, as well as the established aesthetics for graphic designs.

A trifold leaflet and a poster were prepared to be distributed by the partners in physical events and activities but also to be uploaded on the project's website. Both the poster and leaflet are used to attract stakeholders' attention and provide brief information about the SKILLBILL project.

The leaflet presents the project's aim, its vision and its impact, as well as the stakeholders who is benefit from its implementation. The poster focuses more on attracting the stakeholders' attention with graphical elements and offers some basic information on the project and the key stakeholder groups. These will be updated (if needed) in the latest version of SKILLBILL's Dissemination and Communication Plan. Both promotional products provide information about the partners involved, together with their contact details, website and Social Media Accounts (SMAs) as well as acknowledge the funding the project receives through the Horizon Europe program.

Figure 8. SKILLBILL' s leaflet exterior side

Figure 9. SKILLBILL's leaflet interior side

Figure 10. SKILLBILL's poster

5.1.3 Templates

Ensuring uniformity and coherence in all of the project's partners' input documents falls within the scope of the D&C Plan's activities, since by doing so, the project's identity becomes recognizable and the type of document is clarified.

Hence, several templates were prepared with prominent graphic elements that refer to the project's graphical identity (graphic elements in background, header & footer etc.), along with the special aesthetic characteristics of SKILLBILL that make it recognizable.

The following templates have been implemented:

- The SKILLBILL presentation template;
- The template for project deliverables and reports.

In addition to the aforementioned, the SKILLBILL letterhead was created. This graphic element will be used in a variety of project activities, particularly agendas and official events.

The initial versions of the templates presented in the first version of D6.1 did not undergo changes and adjustments after shared with the rest of the consortium for review.

Figure 11. presentation template - front slide

Figure 12. SKILLBILL's presentation template – presentation slide

Figure 14. SKILLBILL's reporting template

Figure 13. SKILLBILL's reporting template - interior

Figure 15. SKILLBILL's letterhead

5.1.4 SKILLBILL's promotional video

Within the framework of the D&C plan's actions, a promotional video has been created by M15 with the goal of attracting public attention to the project's activities and promoting various aspects of the project. The video was posted on SKILLBILL's YouTube channel, the project's website, as well as, in the social media accounts of SKILLBILL (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, etc.).

A breakdown of the video creation process is described as follows. Initially, a video script was drafted by WR outlining the sequence and key phrases that elucidate the project's objectives, SKILLBILL's aims, and approach. The draft version of the script was provided to the rest of the consortium for the partners to share their feedback in order to refine the script. After integrating partners' comments and suggestions, the initial storyboard was created. Further feedback and suggestions on this led to the finalization of the storyboard, and the animated version was then completed and published during November 2023.

The **script** of the video is as follows: “The European Union has set the target of reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, with a focus on the use of renewable energy. To achieve this, the EU recognises the need to equip its workforce with both soft and hard skills. This is where the SKILLBILL project comes in, a three-year Horizon Europe project involving 10 partners from 7 countries. SKILLBILL aims to engage experts, technicians, researchers, entrepreneurs, policy makers and citizens committed to sustainable energy and environmental protection in the new demands of the renewable energy sector. The project offers several benefits: a joint stakeholder initiative addressing the barriers in the renewable energy sector, a green portal with a wealth of information on renewable energy, permanent specialised educational programmes at university level, a vocational training programme using virtual reality for upskilling in the renewable energy sector, and a focus on bridging the gender gap in STEM subjects. The call to action invites you to help shape a sustainable and climate-neutral Europe by supporting SKILLBILL's mission and participating in the organisation's activities via the website and social media. SKILLBILL — Skill to Boost Innovation and professional fulfillment in a sustainable economy - aims to pave the way for a greener future while promoting professional growth and innovation.”

The video's objective is to reach a diverse audience through social networks. It has been uploaded to the project's YouTube channel (accessible here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X-ZecFmlEo8>) and embedded on the project's website. Additionally, it has been shared across all of SKILLBILL's social media accounts. The promotional video serves the purpose of introducing the project in an understandable and visual manner. Given that many terms and concepts used in the project, such as “Renewable Energy Sources”, “Quadruple Helix”, “sustainability” etc., may not be widely known, it is crucial to communicate them at the EU level in a simple and accessible way. Promotional video's goal is to encourage viewers to actively engage with the project.

Figure 16 . Snapshots of SKILLBILL's promotional video on youtube

Table 6. Overview of promotional video KPI up to M18

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current Status (M18)
Views of the promotional video	>5000	175

5.1.5 Other promotional material

In order to enrich the dissemination and communication tools of SKILLBILL project, White Research team developed additional promotional material that maximizes project’s visibility. These materials are:

A promotional banner designed for maximizing project’s visibility, to be used by all consortium partners in external and internal events.

Figure 17. SKILLBILL's promotional banner

A SKILLBILL QR code is also available, designed to guide users to the project's website. It can be incorporated into any materials or presentations created by the partners, ensuring easy access to SKILLBILL's website.

Figure 18. SKILLBILL's QR code

5.2 Digital presence

Gradually, more people choose to get informed through digital communication channels. To better communicate its messages, SKILLBILL is focused on building a strong online presence in multiple digital platforms aiming to reach as many and diverse stakeholders as possible. In particular SKILLBILL has created:

- (i) a weekly updated website;
- (ii) bi-annual newsletters;
- (iii) various SMAs.

5.2.1 SKILLBILL's website

The development of a project website is a crucial step in the dissemination process, since having a functional and user-friendly website boosts SKILLBILL's exposure and impact by presenting the vision, actions, strategies, and progress of the project to a wider audience. An initial version of the SKILLBILL web-portal was launched by M4 (December 2022) of the project, serving as an online platform for informing the public and stakeholders, as well as facilitating communication with the consortium. Since then, we have been updating the website with news and feeds as well as with information related to the project's progress (e.g. Stakeholder Joint Initiative, European Master, Green Portal).³

Figure 19. SKILLBILL's website architecture

The website's architecture (Figure 19) and content is configured to be useful, to fully display the content, object, and actions of SKILLBILL, but also to contain relevant information on project progress, publications resulting from it, and event announcements. The website is featuring all project results, the promotional materials, project deliverables, as well as other helpful information and links, in addition to the fundamental information about the project's content and vision. Thus, the website not only accurately reflects the work that is done and will be done on the project, but it also introduces the visitor to the field of renewable energy sources required to reach a carbon-neutral Europe. Therefore, all partners are expected to supply the relevant material for the content of the

³ The website's URL is as follows: <http://www.skillbill-project.eu/> and project's contact email is info@skillbill-project.eu

SKILLBILL's website development, maintenance and updates. In that way, the website will not only keep visitors up to date on SKILLBILL's actions and results but will also inform them about what is planned during the project.

The website was built using WordPress, with a focus on ensuring responsiveness and accessibility. Special care was taken to make the site compatible with different devices, including mobile ones, to avoid excluding potential visitors.

Indicative snapshots from SKILLBILL website are illustrated below:

Website Homepage

Figure 20. SKILLBILL's website homepage

Key-information on our consortium, mission, concept and approach & related projects

Figure 21. SKILLBILL's website "About us" page

Information about SKILLBILL's Stakeholder Joint Initiative and Working Groups

Figure 22. SKILLBILL's website "Joint Initiative" page

Presentation of SKILLBILL's Green Portal

Figure 23. SKILLBILL website "Green Portal" page

Information about SKILLBILL's European Specialization Program and Vocational Education Training Program

Figure 24. SKILLBILL's website "Skilling, upskilling, reskilling" page

SKILLBILL's resources (reports, dissemination material)

Figure 25. SKILLBILL's website "Resources" page

Project news & events, SKILLBILL's newsletter and related news

Figure 26. SKILLBILL's website "News" page

Contact us information

Figure 27. SKILLBILL's website "Contact us" information page

SKILLBILL's newsletter subscription section

Figure 28. SKILLBILL's newsletter subscription section

5.2.2 Website updates

After the first release of the SKILLBILL website in the first 7 months and with the aim of enriching the content and improving the user experience, the WR team has made several changes and also added new sections in the initially decided architecture. These new sections include published material derived from the project's tasks and outputs (e.g. working groups, published results), additional dissemination materials highlighting the synergies of SKILLBILL, and updates to the sections for related projects and initiatives.

Updates and additions in the "About us" page.

- Advisory board members details and contact information

Figure 29. SKILLBILL's website Advisory Board members' section

- Updated section of related projects & other initiatives which include all project that SKILLBILL has a synergy with.

Figure 30. SKILLBILL website established synergies section

- Public deliverables updated section

Figure 31. SKILLBILL website public deliverables section

Website Analytics

In order to monitor the website visits and downloaded dissemination material we use the Google Analytics service. This tool provides valuable statistics that support us in optimizing SKILLBILL’s website and DC strategy. More specific metrics, also monitored as part of SKILLBILL’s DC plan, are presented in the next sections.

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current Status (M18)
Website/Green Portal visits	≥15,000	Green Portal: 6204 Website: 7946

Overall, SKILLBILL’s website and Green Portal have attracted the interest of diverse stakeholder groups worldwide, as illustrated by the growing number of users and visitors. As of the composition the updated version of D6.1 in January-February 2024, SKILLBILL’s website and Green Portal have over 14.000 visits.

The highlighted visibility of the SKILLBILL website can be attributed to several factors, including:

- (i) The weekly updates featuring project and external news, events related to project’s progress, internal events, participation in external events, and general updates on renewable energy and sustainability sectors.
- (ii) The provision of high-quality information on renewable energy sources, green-education. Skilling-upskilling-reskilling through project’s public deliverables.
- (iii) Linkage to project’s social media accounts by disseminating website articles on these.
- (iv) Wide distribution through engagement and research activities, such as incorporating the website QR code in project presentations and promotional material.

5.2.3 Newsletter

A bi-annual newsletter is produced within the framework of the project and distributed among the project’s community, thus shared with the project’s target audience and posted on the project’s website. Each newsletter offers a recap of the project’s advancements and activities, offering an additional way to update existing subscribers on the project’s outcomes. Additionally, the newsletter functions as a way to engage and keep stakeholders informed, particularly those not active on social media or citizens who may not have shown significant interest in the project during its early stages. The newsletter engages an audience who are not familiar with social media and keeps stakeholders constantly updated about the project. The newsletter, among other things, includes updates on the progress of the project, introduces the project’s concept, and disseminates upcoming project events and activities. **White Research is responsible for releasing the newsletter but, prior to publishing every newsletter, all partners are asked to provide their feedback and insights from the task and activities they lead.**

Mailchimp is used for the development and distribution of the newsletter. Although the content of each issue is agreed upon by the partners, in general, each newsletter includes the following sections:

- An introductory section briefly describing the SKILLBILL project and two project partners in each newsletter, along with their roles in the project.
- Progress updates detailing what has happened in the project, including news of project progress, project meetings, and important milestones.

- Information on current activities that have recently been implemented or are still ongoing.
- A section dedicated to future developments, highlighting upcoming events and important activities.
- A segment focusing on synergies, presenting relevant projects and news from other initiatives.
- News from the sector.

So far, two newsletters have been published. The Newsletters were sent to all the subscribers and recipients upon its release while each issue is also uploaded on the project's website.

A dedicated page on the website has been included in it for the newsletter. On this page, all published newsletters are uploaded together with a subscription section where visitors can enter their contact information to become subscribers to SKILLBILL's newsletter. In terms of subscriptions, all GDPR provisions are also followed in the respective section. When filling out the subscription form, all visitors need to agree to the Privacy Policy, and they have the option to unsubscribe from the newsletter at any time.

Figure 32. SKILLBILL's newsletter section in project's website

Figure 33. SKILLBILL's Privacy Policy on project's website

Below snapshots of the published newsletter are illustrated.

Figure 34. SKILLBILL's 1st newsletter

Figure 35. SKILLBILL's 2nd newsletter

Table 7. Overview of SKILLBILL's newsletter KPIs.

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M18)
Number of newsletters published	6	2
Newsletters subscribers	>300	90

The Newsletter is sent to all subscribers upon its release, and each volume is also posted on the project's website. In general, the SKILLBILL newsletter has demonstrated its effectiveness as a DC tool for connecting with virtual followers. Up to M18, SKILLBILL's newsletter gained 90 subscribers. As engagement activities will continue to increase after M18 due to WP4 and WP5 activities, a continuous increase in subscriber numbers can be expected.

5.2.4 Social media accounts (SMAs)

Social media have proven to be one of the most important pillars set by the D&C plan, as they are widespread tools that can easily and directly promote SKILLBILL 's actions and assets. Specifically, White Research was responsible for setting up the following accounts during M2 (October 2022): Facebook page, Twitter account, LinkedIn account and a YouTube channel. Furthermore, SMAs facilitate the redirection of the audience to the SKILLBILL’s website, often by promoting existing content from the website, thus playing an integral role in our communication strategy. The aim of using social media is to create an online community made up of followers and supporters, which will be maintained and continue to be active even after the end of the project.

The target audiences addressed by each social media channel and the specific objectives are presented in Table 8:

Table 8. SKILLBILL' s Target Audience and Objectives

Social Network	SKILLBILL Target Audience	Objectives
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technology providers ● RES experts ● Innovation Intermediaries ● Policy advisors/makers ● Academic community ● Civil society ● NGOs ● Other stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Building a strong group of followers and exploiting the broader interests of that audience in relation to SKILLBILL ✓ Using of audio-visual promotional material to publicize the project
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SMEs ● Innovation Intermediaries ● Policy advisors/makers ● Civil society ● Financial institutions & investors ● Other stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Enable the effective monitoring of developments and progress in other related projects and relevant organisations ✓ Steer attention towards the concepts and results of SKILLBILL ✓ Identify opportunities for creating synergies with other similar initiatives
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RES experts ● RES Industry ● SMEs ● Innovation Intermediaries ● Policy advisors/makers ● Academic community ● Researchers ● Civil society ● NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Have a more institutional approach in order to boost professional and expert discussions on issues of common interest and possibly involve large corporations, more start-ups, innovation intermediaries and support networks

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Financial institutions & investors ● Other stakeholders 	
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SMEs ● Innovation Intermediaries ● Academic community ● Researchers ● Civil society ● NGOs ● Financial institutions & investors ● Other stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contribution to project's promotion via audio-visual mediums that is going to be made, in order to bring its viewers closer to the object and the faces of SKILLBILL

White Research is responsible for the management and operation of the accounts, nevertheless the consortium partners are expected to support the operation of the social media by:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile);
- Promoting the accounts in their networks;
- Suggesting relevant profiles that SKILLBILL should connect with;
- Sharing interesting articles and news;
- Promoting posts and news through the social media accounts of their own organisations.

Facebook

SKILLBILL's Facebook page was established in M2. The Facebook page is used to promote the project's results and progress and share news about interesting topics from the sector. Different types of posts are created including text and videos. In addition, invitations have been sent to followers for the events organised in the framework of the project. Specifically, SKILLBILL's Facebook account serves as a:

- News and discussion hub where information or updates related to the project and topics of RES and sustainability are shared;
- Platform to deliver updates about developments and results of the project (e.g., published reports, scientific publications, key events, activities, important achievements);
- Link to other similar groups and pages associated with relevant topics.

Figure 36. Snapshot of SKILLBILL's Facebook account

Facebook has proven to be beneficial for disseminating news among followers. Since October 2022, 42 posts have been uploaded on SKILLBILL's Facebook. Our social media strategy has been successful, resulting 63 followers by M18, and facilitating effective communication within the Facebook community.

Twitter

Similarly, the SKILLBILL Twitter account was launched in M2. Twitter is an important dissemination tool for SKILLBILL that enables us to stay updated on the news from the sector and the outcomes from relevant projects. The Twitter platform permit us to establish new synergies with similar initiatives and steer attention towards our concept. The use of hashtags allows the project's messages to reach wider audiences and the short and precise posts' text can actively engage a large pool of stakeholders. In addition, the account is excellent for the effective dissemination of events.

In this context, the Twitter account acts as a:

- General dissemination platform that includes SKILLBILL's key-messages, directs users to other project-related platforms/tools (e.g., SKILLBILL's website, Green Portal, newsletter, promotional video) and communicates information on the project's development (upcoming events, participation to external events, project results, etc.);
- Newsfeed platform collecting and updating news from other relevant projects and organisations;
- Tool to engage and create a community of followers interested in the topic and sector.

The project partners are expected to contribute to the Twitter account on a regular basis by retweeting its content via their personal accounts and suggesting relevant content. Twitter analytics will be used to monitor the account's performance. A snapshot of the account is provided:

Figure 37. Snapshot of SKILLBILL's Twitter account

As of February 29, 2024, SKILLBILL has gathered 1410 tweet impressions and engaged with 30 followers on Twitter. Twitter has proven to be a valuable tool, helping us reach a broader audience by sharing news, updates on upcoming events, and highlights of project activities in a short and simple way. It also serves as a platform for monitoring and participating in interesting conversations on other Twitter accounts, actively contributing to the expansion of SKILLBILL's visibility and network.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn has become an incredibly effective communication tool, especially for connecting with a professional audience. Over the past year and a half, we have used this platform to create and share more than 110 posts, strategically promoting our project to a target audience.

Our project's profile on LinkedIn, located in M2, serves as a hub to present comprehensive project details and constantly update our audience on the project's progress. We specifically chose LinkedIn to target a more professional audience that aligns with the goals of the project.

WR team continuously encourages SKILLBILL partners to actively support the LinkedIn profile of our project by inviting followers and participating in discussions. The SKILLBILL page itself has a more institutional character and promotes professional dialogue on topics of common interest, increasing the visibility of the project. We are aware of the importance of analyses in the evaluation of performance. To this end, we use the metrics and insights provided by LinkedIn to measure the impact of the project and refine our communication strategy accordingly. LinkedIn is not just a platform, but an important tool to foster meaningful connections, increase engagement and measure the reach of our project in the professional community.

Figure 38. SKILLBILL's LinkedIn page.

As of February 29, 2024, SKILLBILL has connected with 687 followers on LinkedIn, gaining more than 47,000 impressions. By using LinkedIn, SKILLBILL can stay informed about renewable energy sector developments and take part in professional discussions on topics of shared interest across

various professional networks. This channel is anticipated to further enhance the project's visibility among stakeholders interested in taking part in renewable energy education and the skilling-reskilling-upskilling concept.

YouTube Channel

The last established channel which was also created on M2 is YouTube. The project's channel is used to increase the visibility of the project through videos. In particular, the promotional video of the project, which was published on M15, is uploaded in SKILLBILL's YouTube channel to raise awareness around the project and promoted using all project's social media account. The SKILLBILL YouTube channel is focused on presenting the project's actions and especially the results. Besides the video, the channel's aim is to build a strong online community through the connection with other channels of EU funded projects.

Figure 39. Snapshot of SKILLBILL's YouTube channel

As of the writing of this report in February 2024, SKILLBILL's YouTube channel had 11 subscribers, while the promotional video had a total of 175 views.

The overall progress of SKILLBILL social media followers up to M18 is presented in the following table.

Table 9. Overview of SKILLBILL's social media KPIs.

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current Status (M18)
Followers on social media	≥5,000	772

5.3 Events

5.3.1 Internal events

In the frame of SKILLBILL, several events are organised to serve the project's objectives and promote the project and its outcomes. As such are defined the events which are organized as part of the GA agreement. In more detail, the following types of events are scheduled as part of the project's plan:

Table 10. SKILLBILL's internal events catalogue

Event	Task; partner	Short Description	Date	Status
Digital Co-creation Workshops	T2.2; QP	Participants were introduced to our ideas and initial design and along with them we co-defined the specificities of the stakeholder joint initiative.	M10	Completed (Link)
Online Working Group Meetings	T2.3 QP	A set of 4 online meetings were organized in November 2023, one per relevant Working Group formulated (Sustainable and Renewable Electricity, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable and Renewable Heat, Sustainable and Renewable Fuels). The Working Group meetings are organized by QP but the discussions are facilitated by selected Lighthouse Experts. Participants were engaged experts on the different fields. The output of the first WG meetings were solutions and recommendations identified by the experts.	M15	Completed (Link)
Online Working Group Meetings	T2.3; QP	The second set of 4 online WG meetings will be organized in May 2024, targeting in delivering regulatory shifts and recommendations	M21	To be scheduled
Online Working Group Meetings	T2.3; QP	The third set of 4 online WG meetings will be organized in November 2024, to develop guidelines for education and training programmes.	M27	To be scheduled
Online Working Group Meetings	T2.3; QP	The fourth online WG meeting is a plenary meeting inviting the experts of all 4 WGs. It will be organized in November 2024.	M33	To be scheduled
Mobilisation and Mutual Learning	T2.4; PC	During these workshops, the experiences and results of WP2, WP4 and WP5 will be shared and discussed to produce actionable knowledge that can improve	1 st : M28 2 nd : M34	To be scheduled

(MML) Workshops		them, all while raising awareness and stimulating their practical application in different contexts by participating stakeholders.		
Final event	T6.2; WR	We will present the project's results to an international audience and set the stage for their uptake after the project's completion.	M36	To be scheduled

Workshops/Promotional activities

Completed and ongoing events and promotional activities

Digital Co-creation Workshop (T2.2)

Q-PLAN organized the Digital Co-Creation Workshop on June 24th2023. The workshop was organized with the support of all partners, where diverse group of 32 participants, including external stakeholders, experts on renewable energy across the quadruple helix, advisory board members, and consortium partners, came together with a shared vision of advancing renewable energy. The results of the workshop were documented and delivered in the dedicated D2.2. report (read the full report [here](#)).

The primary focus of the workshop was to establish four thematic working groups, each with a unique emphasis on critical aspects of the renewable energy sector. These working groups will serve as collaborative hubs, facilitating the exchange of ideas and expertise among experts and enthusiasts alike, and their Focus is summarized in:

1. Sustainable and Renewable Electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential.
2. Sustainable Mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential.
3. Sustainable and Renewable Heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential.
4. Sustainable and Renewable Fuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential.

With the formation of these strategic working groups, we aim to harness the collective intelligence of industry professionals and specialists. Their valuable insights will guide us in navigating the challenges and opportunities within the renewable energy landscape.

Figure 40. Snapshot's of SKILLBILL's digital co-creation workshop under T2.2

WR promoted the report through SKILLBILL social media accounts and the newsletter. During the preparation and implementation stage of the workshops, WR assisted through dissemination actions, such as posting on social media, inviting key stakeholders, etc.

European Specialization Program promotional activity (T4.6)

Promotional activities aim to inform potential students about the course's existence and related opportunities (e.g., internships and stages). To achieve this goal, WR implemented a dedicated page on the project website along with targeted info that was added on each partner's institutional website. In terms of dissemination and communication activities, social media and traditional communication channels were used to this purpose. WR uploaded the relevant material prepared by UniTus with the help of MET, USE, UU on the project's website and promotes it on social media accounts. WR also provides any other necessary help through dissemination actions, such as posting on social media and inviting key stakeholders, etc. Specialization Program's syllabus was also uploaded on SKILLBILL's website together (read the full Syllabus [here](#)) with program's promotional material.

PROJECT ID

Project name: Skill to Boost Innovation and professional SkillSet in a sustainable economy
 Grant Agreement: 101075587
 Programme: Horizon Europe
 Type of action: HORIZON-CSA
 Start date: 1 September 2022
 Duration: 36 months
 EU contribution: 2.493.640,00€
 Coordinator: AzzeroCO SRL

OUR TEAM

- AzzeroCO SRL <https://www.azzero.co2.it/> Italy
- Q-PLAN International Advisors PC <https://qplanintl.gr/> Greece
- White Research SRL <https://white-research.eu/> Belgium
- UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA <https://www.univ.tus.it/> Italy
- UNIVERSITÄT DUISBURG ESSEN <https://www.uni-due.de/> Spain
- Metropolia Ammattikorkeakoulu Oy <https://www.metropolia.fi/> Finland
- Utrecht University <https://www.uu.nl/> Netherlands
- EREF European Renewable Energies Federation <https://erf-europe.org/> Belgium
- SINERGIE S.p.A. <https://www.sinergieitalia.com/> Italy
- PEDAL Consulting s.r.l. <https://pedalconsulting.eu/> Slovakia

COORDINATOR: AzzeroCO SRL

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skillbill PRESENTS

European Specialisation School in Sustainable Energy

www.skillbill-project.eu

THE SCHOOL IN A NUTSHELL

- Creating professionals able and willing to lead the energy transition
- Focus on renewable energy technologies and on the socio-economic aspects of energy transition
- Traditional and live streaming lessons between 4 PM and 8 PM
- All lessons will be recorded
- Extensive use of Virtual Reality for an enhanced learning experience

Legal facts:

- **Course duration:** 1 academic year
- **Number of ECTS:** 60 ECTS
- **Number of exams:** 8 + Final dissertation
- **EQF Levels:** level 7
- **Fees:** Waived until 2025
- **Available positions:** 50
- **Applications deadline:** OPEN up to October 30, 2023
- **Admission requirements:** BSc in Engineering, Physics, Mathematics, Chemistry or Economics.
- **Required documents:** CV, motivational letter, valid ID, BSc diploma certificate
- **How to apply:** by email to didatticasi@unitus.it

Read the syllabus for additional info.

THE 6 PILLARS:

4 vertical and 2 horizontal integrated pillars guarantee a global vision of energy transition and the ability to re-think energy design and research.

Sustainability, circularity, and socio-economic aspects of energy transition

Renewable and Sustainable Fuels, Renewable and Sustainable Heat, Renewable and Sustainable Electricity, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainability, Circularity, and Socio-Economic Aspects of Energy Transition, System Integration, Energy Management, Storage and Efficiency

THE TEAM

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA, UNIV. DUISBURG ESSEN, Metropolia, Utrecht University

Modules and exams

Organization of courses and lessons - highlighted modules: compulsory / [VR] virtual reality available

Period	Renewable and Sustainable Fuels	Renewable and Sustainable Heat	Renewable and Sustainable Electricity	Sustainable Mobility	Sustainability, Circularity, and Socio-Economic Aspects of Energy Transition	System Integration, Energy Management, Storage and Efficiency
1	Infra		Renewable Energy: The Power, Grid and Energy Efficiency			Energy Management
2	Hydro to Lake	Renewable Heat: The Technology and the Socio-Economic Aspects	Variable Renewable Energy Technologies in	Grid Impact	Water Energy Nexus	
3		Renewable Heat: The Technology and the Socio-Economic Aspects	Renewable Energy: The Power, Grid and Energy Efficiency	AI Energy	Sustainability in the Context of	Energy Storage
4	Renew to X	Renewable Heat: The Technology and the Socio-Economic Aspects		Alternative Transport	Climate Resilience	Hydrogen Systems

Internship - Thesis - Final dissertation

For further information about the School, please visit the website at skillbill-project.eu/skilling-up/skilling-reskilling/european-master/

Figure 41. European Specialization Program Promotional Material

Future events and promotional activities

SKILLBILL's next Working Groups (T2.3)

The upcoming rounds of Working Groups (WGs) are poised to further support our endeavors towards fostering regulatory shifts and offering valuable recommendations. Scheduled for May 2024, the second set of four online WG meetings will be dedicated to meticulously crafting strategies aimed at delivering impactful regulatory changes. Following this, in November 2024, the third set of four online WG meetings will aim to develop comprehensive guidelines tailored for education and training programs. Moreover, this period will also include a pivotal plenary meeting aiming to highlight these discussions, inviting experts from all four WGs to synthesize collective insights and create a path forward. Through these strategic activities, SKILLBILL aims not only to harness the expertise of its stakeholders but also to bring up advancements in regulatory frameworks and educational practices.

Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) Workshops (T2.4)

In line with the work of the Working Groups under Task 2.3 and building on their outputs, a series of Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops will be organized by PC. The workshops will utilize a co-creative bottom-up approach to collect suggestions, recommendations, and ideas for further improving the outputs of the working groups. During these workshops, the experiences and results of WP2, WP4, and WP5 will be shared and discussed to produce actionable knowledge that could improve our work, all while raising awareness and stimulating the practical application in different contexts by the participating stakeholders. During the preparation and implementation stages of the workshops, WR will deploy dissemination and stakeholder engagement tools for that, such as press releases, website news, SMAs posts, etc.

Final dissemination event (T6.2)

The SKILLBILL's Final Conference will be organized by WR close to the end of SKILLBILL with the support of all partners, to spread accumulated knowledge and present final achievements to RPOs, RFOs, policy makers and broadly to all interested parties. To maximise the outreach of this event, we will seek to organise it as a satellite event at a larger international event (e.g., European Science Engagement Conference) and/or in collaboration with one or more sister projects.

It must be underlined that the above mentioned working groups, workshops and conferences are an essential part of the SKILLBILL's DC Plan. The organisers of the abovementioned events are required to fill in a template (i.e., Event Reporting Template) in which they will present the main communication and/or dissemination action(s) that took place.

5.3.2 External events and conferences

The participation of the consortium partners in external events, conferences, and exhibitions is an opportunity for the project to approach a wider audience with a variety of backgrounds. Throughout the duration of SKILLBILL, the partners continuously participate in external events with the aim of:

- Presenting SKILLBILL's concept;
- Keeping in touch with the latest developments in the field;
- Disseminating the knowledge gathered during SKILLBILL;
- Developing relationships with stakeholders;
- Promoting the activities and results of the project;
- Overall raising awareness.

To ensure uniformity and common aesthetics of the project's presentations and means of communication, consortium partners, have at their disposal the leaflet, the poster, the template for the slides, and for the publications. In all these project's dissemination and communication tools, the same colors will be chosen, and the project logo will be prominently included. Presentations made at external events and intended to highlight SKILLBILL's concept, goals & events must use the specific templates, and their content must be sent to White Research and AzzeroCO2 at least 5 working days before the event. An indicative list of identified conferences and events is provided in Table 11.

SKILLBILL's project coordinator, Azzero, participated at:

1. [European Sustainable Energy Week 2023](#);
2. [CH4 Expo 2023](#)

Additionally, Pedal, a consortium partner, participated in the following events:

1. [SmartCity Expo Barcelona 2023](#): Showcased by PEDAL Consulting in Urban Innovation;
2. [9th SBA Professional Conference – The Future of Slovak Biogas 2023](#).
3. Final conference of RESTART project

These events served as platforms for showcasing the SKILLBILL project, networking, and highlighting its contributions to urban innovation and sustainable energy initiatives.

Table 11. SKILLBILL's external events and conferences (indicative)

Conference	Short Description	Link
Ecomondo + Key Energy	Annual fair held addressed to the eco-industries and actors of energy sectors, for ecological transition and new models of circular economy	https://en.ecomondo.com/
EU Sustainable Energy Week	The biggest EU conference dedicated to RES and efficient energy. EREF, has submitted an application to organise a policy session at the European Sustainable Energy Week 2024 that would be running under the title "Skills to accelerate the deployment of renewable energies".	https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/index_en
EU Green Week	EU Green Week <u>brings</u> together all stakeholders and citizens to make the reach a zero-pollution, toxic-free environment.	https://www.eugreenweekpartnerevents2022.eu/
EUBCE	European Biomass Conference & Exhibit is the largest biomass conference and exhibition in the world.	https://www.eubce.com/
IEA bioenergy	IEA bioenergy organizes and frequently Conferences on Biofuels & Bioenergy.	https://www.ieabioenergy.com/
MakerFaire	The most important innovation event in technological field, brings together technologists, universities, educators, businesses, to share knowledge and find inspiration.	https://makerfaire.com/

Servdes	Service Design and Innovation Conference is the premier research conference for exchanging knowledge within Service Design and service innovation studies.	https://servdes.org/about-servdes/
Women in Energy Summit	The Women-in-Energy Program is the first targeted initiative to advance women in the energy sector in the Central and West Asia region. The goal is to make the principles of EQUAL by 2030 the modus operandi in the region's energy industry, making equal opportunity, equal pay, and equal leadership the new standard by 2030.	https://women-energy-summit.org/
Women IN Energy Conference	The Women IN Energy Conference provides an opportunity for women to learn and engage in thoughtful, relevant discussions. The conference features a keynote speaker, a panel, and several unique and engaging breakout sessions, as well as opportunities for networking.	https://wewomeninenergy.com/events/women-in-energy-conference/
Women Energize Women" (WEW) Conference	The conference is a highlight of the "Women Energize Women" communication campaign that has been implemented by GIZ in collaboration with the German Renewable Energy Federation (BEE) within the framework of the Bilateral Energy Partnerships (EP) and on behalf of the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK).	m/events/women-in-energy-conference/

Up to M18 SKILLBILL consortium participated in 4 external events. The updated version of the DCP provides a list of indicative conferences and events where SKILLBILL partners have participated and disseminated the project.

Table 12. Attended events up to M18

No.	Event's name	Date	Website	Partner
1	European Sustainable Energy Week	20-22 Jun. 2023	Link	A0
2	CH4 Expo 2023	11 Oct. 2023	Link	A0
3	FemPower Summer School 2023	2 Sep. 2023	Link	WR
4	9th SBA Professional Conference - The Future of Slovak Biogas 2023	19-20 Oct. 2023	Link	PC
5	Final conference of RESTART project	25 Oct. 2023	Link	PC
6	SmartCity Expo World Congress	7-9 Nov. 2023	Link	PC

5.4 Publications

During SKILLBILL partners are encouraged to use publications to promote several significant project achievements. These publications are among the most valuable assets of the project because they reveal and secure the new education and training practices that will be generated as a result of SKILLBILL to deeply engage and educate stakeholders in sustainable energy & renewable energy sources. According to the dissemination strategy, at least 5 scientific / generalist papers should be published. In addition to these, partners may propose any other publication that will help to display and promote the project's results.

An indicative list of scientific Journals can be found below:

Table 13. Indicative list of pre-selected scientific journals for SKILLBILL publications

Journal	Impact Factor
Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	15.9
Sustainable Cities and Society	12.9
Energy Research and Social Science	8.29
Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions	7.2
Sustainability	3.9
International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education	3.68

6. Roles and responsibilities

All the members of the consortium play a key role in SKILLBILL's communication activities, in order to fulfil the goals and objectives set by the D&C plan and, thus, to achieve its optimal functioning. The participation and contribution of partners directly affect project's development, such as the activities, results, and overall progress, which will be promoted through dissemination activities and communication tools.

Therefore, partners will keep on assisting and supporting SKILLBILL's online presence during the second half of the project, both by providing appropriate material for social media and website posts, and by promoting the posts in order to gain more followers who will stay informed about SKILLBILL's actions and results. Furthermore, partners are continuously encouraged to support the project's wider promotion by attending relevant events/conferences and publishing in online and offline publications (e.g. websites, newspapers, magazines etc.).

At the end of each project month, all partners are expected fill out the **Dissemination Reporting template** to present the main dissemination and communication actions they carried out during the month (Annex 2). The organizing of events, taking part in events, informal gatherings, interviews, communication campaigns (such as newsletter distribution, leaflet distribution, etc.), publishing, training, and other activities are examples of dissemination acts included in this template.

In addition to the Dissemination Reporting template, partners are asked to complete the Conferences and Events templates (Annex 3 & 4) for each event they either organised or participated in, presenting the main dissemination actions that occurred in that specific event in order to track all the events in timely manner.

All partners' responsibilities and expected activities are summarised in the following table.

Table 14. Partner's responsibilities

Activity	Partners' responsibility
Online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Provide content for the website, SMAs and the newsletter (The contribution could be a suggestion for a Facebook or Twitter post, an article regarding the project or a relevant topic of the sector, or an interview). The goals are to ensure a constant flow of content around the project's actions and keep our online presence active and useful for the relevant stakeholders. ➔ Promote the website, SMAs and the newsletter through their network. ➔ Inform the dissemination manager about relevant events or news of the sector that could be used for content creation.
Offline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Organise events and raise awareness on the project results and main topics. ➔ Disseminate the promotional material of the project (leaflet, poster, etc.). ➔ All partners through their participation in external events and conferences and through publications for online/ offline sources (websites, newspapers, magazines, etc.) should ensure the widest exposure and dissemination of the project.
Reporting	All partners must report the carried-out dissemination and communication activities to the dissemination manager. More information for the process will follow in the respective chapter.

7. Networks and synergies

The establishment of synergies and the use of networks for the dissemination of the project's results is pivotal for its successful implementation. This need was identified from the proposal stage and therefore a dedicated task (T6.5) that aims to search for alignment with opportunities with relevant projects was included.

Over the course of the project the SKILLBILL partners:

1. Cooperates with the projects which are funded under the same call (RES4CITY, SEANERGY, TRANSIT).
2. Seeks and establishes synergies with projects that are relevant to the topic.

The cooperation may take various forms. Indicatively:

- Mutual communication/ dissemination of events in our social media accounts and website;
- Mutual reference of projects on respective websites;
- Organisation of joint activities (e.g., workshops, communication/ dissemination events etc.);
- Participation in the project's events;
- Exchange of news, experiences;
- Co-participate in conferences;
- Co-write press releases, articles etc.

Multiple potential joint activities will be also identified throughout the whole duration of the project and will be reported in the respective deliverable.

Even from the initial stages of the project several potential networks and relevant projects have been identified. In addition to the mutual synergies on the activities, some members of the SKILLBILL Advisory Board are also involved in the projects listed in the table below (the Project Leader of RES4CITY; GreenSkills4H2); likewise, SKILLBILL's project leader is also an AB member of RES4CITY.

Table 15. Projects for potential synergies

Acronym	Title	Description	Website	Period
BeFlex	Boosting Engagement to increase FLEXibility	"BeFlex aims at increasing energy system flexibility, enhancing cooperation among DSOs and TSOs and easing participation of all energy-related actors through the validation and large-scale demonstration of adapted and proven cross-sectoral services." ⁴	Link	9/2022-8/2026
ENFLATE	ENabling FLEXibility provision by all	"ENFLATE project will build upon existing solutions on data driven energy services and non-energy	Link	9/2022-8/2026

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101075438>

	Actors and sectors through markets and digital TEchnologies	services, and replicate them in different geographies, climate and consumer needs” ⁵		
SMEnergy	Service centres and transformation path for a bigger share of renewable energy use of SMEs	Aims to create a pilot network of regional/county-wide service centres to support energy-intensive SMEs in accelerating their transition to renewable energy.	Link	N/A
ST(R)E(A)M IT	ST(R)E(A)M IT/STREAMING girls and women into steam education, innovation and research	The main objective of ST(R)E(A)M IT is to initiate change in persisting gender inequalities in STEM education, research, and innovation in order to contribute to the ‘The European Manifesto for gender-inclusive STE(A)M education and careers.’	Link	1/2024-12/2026

Table 16. SKILLBILL’s dissemination networks

Network (name)	Short description	Link
WISTER	“The women’s network Wister provides information on gender issues, particularly with regard to new technologies and to promote innovation policies. It recognizes the needs and the skills of women in research, as well as in projects and debates on innovation, and it aims to increase the presence of women in ICT careers. On their website, you will find interviews, news and events”	https://www.wister.it/
EU Bioeconomy Network	“The European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet) is a proactive alliance of 114 EU funded projects and initiatives dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication and support. The main goal is to maximise the efforts, increasing the knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, coordination of joint activities and events.”	https://eubionet.eu/

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101075783>

<p>Greek International Business Association (SEVE)</p>	<p>“The Greek Exporters Association (SEVE) was established in 1975 as a non-profit organisation and is currently the largest association of exporting companies in Greece. SEVE’s members include manufacturers, distributors and service providers of a broad spectrum of products and services.”</p>	<p>https://www.seve.gr</p>
<p>EU Alliance for Innovation (EAI)</p>	<p>“European Alliance for Innovation (EAI) is a non-profit organisation and a professional community empowering global research and innovation, promoting cooperation between European and International ICT communities around the globe.”</p>	<p>https://eai.eu</p>
<p>Innovation World Network (INWN)</p>	<p>“An international network connecting organisations which provide combined and integrated services in the areas of project proposal preparation, project administration and consultancy. They start with building the right strategy for your idea and move to implementing the project. Their network partners have been consulting local and international organisations since 2007”</p>	<p>https://inwn.eu</p>
<p>TENDERIO</p>	<p>“Tenderio combines a pan-European network of consultancy firms specialised in public procurement with the leading public tender search engine for SMEs. Our service helps SMEs identify possible partners and recommends expert consultancies to help write bids and translate materials into the appropriate language.”</p>	<p>https://www.tenderio.com</p>
<p>Cluster Build</p>	<p>“The BUILD Clust-ER is an association of public and private organisations (companies, research centres and training institutions) that aims to support the innovation system in the building and construction field, developing collaborative research and technology transfer activities, according to the priorities of the Emilia Romagna Region Smart Specialization Strategy”</p>	<p>https://build.clust-er.it</p>
<p>KIRAHub</p>	<p>“KIRAHub is a multifaceted and transparent ecosystem of the real estate and construction industry. “KIRAHub’s vision is to make Finland the forerunner in the sustainable digitalization of the built environment.</p>	<p>https://kirahub.org</p>
<p>ERRIN</p>	<p>“The European Regions Research and Innovation Network (ERRIN) is a well-known Brussels-based platform that gathers around 120 regional organisations from more than 20 European countries. Established in 2001, ERRIN supports members to enhance their regional and local research and innovation capacities and further develop their R&I ecosystems.”</p>	<p>https://errin.eu/</p>

U!REKA	“As an international applied research, innovation and education network with common goals, U!REKA’s ambition is to educate, shape and deliver the European professionals of tomorrow. These professionals contribute to an inclusive, intercultural and open-minded professional Europe.	https://www.ureka.eu
Hydrogen-Europe	“Hydrogen Europe is the European association representing the interest of the hydrogen industry and its stakeholders and promoting hydrogen as an enabler of a zero-emission society.”	https://hydrogeneurope.eu
Eurofusion	“European Consortium for the Development of Fusion Energy was born from fusion research bodies from European Union member states and Switzerland. Presently EUROfusion supports and funds fusion research activities on behalf of the European Commission’s Euratom programme within 26 EU member states.”	https://www.eurofusion.org

Up to M18 SKILLBILL has established 7 synergies with other EU funded projects. A table with the names, logos, descriptions and websites links of the synergy projects is illustrated below (Table 17). SKILLBILL project remains focused on identifying new projects and initiatives for collaborations, in order not only to reach the KPI of more than 10 synergy projects by the end of the project but also to stay in close contact with them for being supported mutually.

Table 17. Established Synergies

Project short name	Full Name	Short description	Website
SEANERGY 	Sustainability EducationAI programme for greeNER fuels and enerGY on ports	“Aims to provide a solution for exploiting the untapped potential of EU-ports energy’s system by implementing the SEANERGY Master Plan which assesses stakeholders to execute the necessary activities towards transforming ports, regardless of their geographical context, into active members of the clean energy and fuel generation grid of EEZ.” ⁶	Link

⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101075710>

<p>TRANSIT</p>	<p>TRANSITION to sustainable future through training and education</p>	<p>“Aims to provide sustainable training and reskilling programmes for current and future generations on a multidisciplinary approach in renewable energy and fuel technologies, identifying global and local challenges to realise the large deployment ambitions, covering European level and all different stakeholders' levels.”⁷</p>	<p>Link</p>
<p>RES4CITY</p>	<p>Upskilling students and members of the workforce to prepare for the green transition, in support of a low carbon economy</p>	<p>RES4CITY is a 36-month project, starting in Q4-2022, and funded by the European Union, that aims to enhance the development of sustainable renewables and fuel technologies in cities by co-designing an innovative educational programme with stakeholders and promoting sustainability and circularity, filling the knowledge and skills gaps for a successful energy transition.</p>	<p>Link</p>
<p>ALFA</p>	<p>Scaling up the market uptake of Renewable Energy Systems by unlocking the biogas potential of Agriculture and Livestock Farming</p>	<p>“ALFA supports at least 50 livestock farmers in 6 EU countries (IT, DK, DE, BE, SK, EL, ES) to overcome existing barriers and viably take up biogas systems. We start by establishing regional Hubs that analyse the local framework conditions and livestock value chains, and help engage local stakeholders in co-designing our approach”⁸</p>	<p>Link</p>
<p>W4RES</p>	<p>Women for market uptake of renewable heating and cooling</p>	<p>The project aims at the involvement of women to support market uptake of Renewable Heating and Cooling</p>	<p>Link</p>

⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101075747>

⁸ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101075659>

<p>GreenSkills4H2</p>	<p>Design of a reactive and urgent upskilling and reskilling programme for occupational profiles for a career in the Hydrogen value chain</p>	<p>The 4-year project aims at developing sectoral skills strategies to reduce skills shortages, gaps and mismatches, in the short and the medium term.</p>	<p>Link</p>
<p>FemPower</p>	<p>Gender Equality in the Clean Energy Transition</p>	<p>FemPower is a Cooperation Partnership in Higher Education. FemPower aims to increase female representation in the sector, empower and prepare those who are already active in academia or the market, and integrate the gender dimension in CET research and development.</p>	<p>Link</p>

8. Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting framework

8.1 Monitoring and KPIs progress evaluation

Monitoring

The implementation of the dissemination & communication plan is monitored throughout the whole project in terms of the consistency of what is foreseen and the corresponding results. The continuous evaluation of dissemination activities allows for the monitoring and quantitative assessment of the impact of actions. Thus, deviations from the original plan can be visible on time, and necessary changes are made to continuously increase the project's visibility and dissemination of its results. WR is in charge of monitoring and evaluating SKILLBILL's dissemination activities, but the project consortium is expected to work collaboratively, being aware of their activities and results at all times.

A set of KPIs were selected to evaluate the impact of the DCP activities (Table 18). Of course, the metric targets and the needs are continuously adjusted to the project's results and will be included in the final Dissemination and Communication Plan (M36). The dissemination manager (WR) with the support of the consortium partners will keep track of the quantitative metrics during the reporting periods. In addition, qualitative feedback after the implementation of events will be also requested by the partners to better evaluate the strategy and proceed with modifications if deemed necessary.

Table 18. SKILLBILL's Key Performance Indicators

Assessed element	Metric	Target	Current Status (M1-M18)
Visits to SKILLBILL website	No. of visits	≥ 15,000	Green Portal:6204 Website: 7946 Total: 14,150
Social media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter)	No. of followers	≥ 5,000	769
	No. of impressions	≥ 50,000	47,000
Publications	No. scientific / generalist papers	≥ 5	-
Newsletter	No. of newsletters	6	2
	No. of subscribers	≥ 300	90
Promotional material	<i>No. of material distributed</i>	<i>≥ 300</i>	<i>471 (KPI reached)</i>
Participation in external events	No. of events	≥ 15	6
Promotional video	No. of views	≥ 5,000	173
Synergies with other projects	No. of synergies	>10	7
Final dissemination event	No. of participants	≥ 80	To be scheduled
Green Portal	No. of uploaded materials	≥ 300	147
	No. of labelled material	≥ 500	147

KPIs progress evaluation

Given the dynamic nature of digital communication today and the mid-term of SKILLBILL, it is important to assess the evolution of the key performance indicators (KPIs) in terms of dissemination and communication activities. Considering that all internet users are overwhelmed by the constant stream of digital information via different channels (e.g. social media and websites), the pace of KPI development for certain KPIs (e.g. number of social media followers and number of views of promotional videos) can seem relatively slow. However, it's crucial to recognize that **the effectiveness of dissemination efforts extends beyond the KPI set during the GA phase.**

Despite the perceived slow KPI's progression in certain KPIs, alternative indicators shed light on the considerable impact of SKILLBILL's dissemination and communication activities. The joint commitment of the SKILLBILL consortium is constantly extending the reach of the project. If the partners publish new posts on their LinkedIn accounts, for example, the visibility of the project is increased in their respective networks. This domino effect ensures that a wide audience (**totalling more than 4000 LinkedIn users from the consortium partners' accounts**) remains informed about SKILLBILL's activities and successes beyond the direct SKILLBILL followers or subscribers. Since the launch of SKILLBILL's LinkedIn account, more than **47000 LinkedIn impressions, 2000 reactions and 160 reposts** have already been counted.

Moreover, the distribution of promotional materials serves as a tangible touchpoint for individuals who may not actively engage with digital platforms (**more than 470 copies were distributed**). While they may not be directly connected to SKILLBILL's online channels, exposure to promotional materials cultivates awareness and familiarity with the project's objectives. Similarly, participation in internally organized workshops (e.g. **32 participants in CCW under T2.2**); research activities (e.g. **31 interviewees under T2.1**) and knowledge-sharing events (e.g. **41 experts of SKILLBILL Working Groups**) foster the dissemination of experience gained by project's activities on a broader scale.

Based on this multi-dimensional approach, it's evident that the impact of dissemination and communication efforts goes beyond the KPI metrics agreed at the GA. Although quantitative indicators provide valuable insights, qualitative feedback gathered from events participation, partners' active engagement through their social media and project's internal events offer alternative perspectives essential for refining dissemination strategies. Even if the development of the KPIs appears to be gradual, the holistic assessment of SKILLBILL's dissemination landscape emphasises the project's great influence and popularity among its target group.

8.2 Reporting

Keeping track of the dissemination, communication and engagement activities that were carried out by all partners in the framework of the project is fundamental for its successful implementation. Therefore, the reporting and documentation is very important for the DCP. In particular, throughout the duration of the project, all consortium partners should report their dissemination and communication activities on a monthly basis by filling in the template shared by White Research (online in the project's repository). Each semester (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36) White Research consolidates the results and will develop the semestrial technical reporting of WP6.

For keeping track of the activities performed by the consortium partners, three documents have been designed and shared (Annex).

Table 19. List of Annexes for dissemination

Annex	Dissemination Tool	Coverage	When
Annex II	Dissemination reporting template	All the dissemination activities carried out by the partners every month.	Every month
Annex III	Event's reporting template	Each single event organised by the partners or where the partners participated.	Within 30 days after the implementation of the event
Annex IV	External conferences and Events template	Any external event/conference that it is relevant to our project and with potential benefit to attend	Throughout the project (ad-hoc basis)

Dissemination reporting template: This template records all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The document should be updated monthly by all partners. Keeping track of the activities ensures that any problems or gaps are observed early, and mitigation measures will be put in place in order to be solved.

Event reporting template: This template should be filled by all partners whenever they organise or participate in an event (e.g., workshop, conference, meeting etc.). The template should be sent to White Research and AzzeroCO2 no later than 30 days after the implementation of the event. Moreover, the events should be always communicated to White Research and AzzeroCO2 in advance for promotional purposes.

The external conferences and Events template: This is a template that facilitates the identification of events (workshops, conferences, webinars) with topics relevant to the SKILLBILL vision. Each partner should fill in this template and send the information to White Research and AzzeroCO2 when identifying any event or conference that could be useful for the consortium (e.g., attend, present etc.).

Each project partner should immediately contact White Research and AzzeroCO2, should any risks be identified concerning communication and dissemination activities, or in case problems arise during the implementation of publicity actions.

9. Timeline and implementation plan

To ensure that the timing of dissemination and communication, as well as stakeholder engagement, is effectively implemented, the actions were divided into four phases, as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 42. Summary of SKILLBILL'S timeline

The four stages are listed below:

- ❖ **Early in the project:** The Dissemination & Communication strategy was designed, while the targeted stakeholder groups and the key messages of the project were identified. Further, suitable metrics for monitoring the successful implementation of the D&C strategy were also selected. Additionally, the consortium partners were informed about their responsibilities and required contributions in relation to dissemination efforts.

Overall, in this phase, our actions are continuously dedicated to the general promotion of the project, emphasizing awareness raising to ensure that the project is widely communicated. In that context, during the first six months of the project, the logo and visual identity were designed along with the project's website. Further, the social media accounts of the project were launched, and the dissemination material (leaflets, posters, templates, letterhead) were produced. The promotional package is expected to be later enriched with evidence and success stories from the project to communicate its benefits if needed. By month 6, all project tools and channels were developed. Moreover, some first synergies with other relevant projects/initiatives were established. Finally, at this stage, the project was additionally disseminated in networking events in which partners would participate.

- ❖ **During the project:** We continue seeking to cluster and cooperate with complementary projects and initiatives relevant to the topic of education and RES. Additionally, an active community interested in the SKILLBILL's project is continuously established and engaged through the project's SMAs and website, where the project's results are shared, while bi-annual newsletters are also released. In addition, SKILLBILL's promotional video was published during 15.

Further, a variety of dissemination events (co-creation and digital workshops, mutual learning workshops, webinars, networking events with sister projects, awareness raising and education events) are scheduled to take place. Finally, the consortium partners are expected to continuously support dissemination efforts by participating in external events and conferences, while leveraging existing platforms, networks and initiatives.

- ❖ **At the end of the project:** During this stage, the project's key results will be further disseminated. The project's SMAs will remain active to ensure that project's outcomes are publicised. The milestone of that phase is hosting the final dissemination event of the project in which the project's results and findings will be presented.
- ❖ **Beyond the end of the project:** Consortium partners have agreed to promote and exploit project results even after the project has ended through future activities, new projects, and so on. The main goal is for industries, civil society organisations, governments and policy makers, academia and science and other stakeholders to act as multipliers for project adoption and further promotion. Furthermore, even after the project's official completion, relevant publications will continue to disseminate its legacy.

SKILLBILL's implementation plan is presented in the following table:

Table 20. SKILLBILL implementation plan

Phase	Objectives	Dissemination and Communication tools to be used
1st Phase (M1-M6)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Design the D&C strategy of SKILLBILL 2. Design the logo and the visual identity of the project 3. Prepare the promotional package (leaflet, poster, templates, letterheads) 4. Set – up the project's digital dissemination tools (social media accounts, website) 5. Announce the project widely 6. Set up the first synergies with relevant projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project's DCP - Project's logo - Project's website - Project's SMAs - Project's poster, leaflet, presentation and report templates, letterheads - Project's press release - Project's newsletter - Contact with other projects and networks - Participation in external events
2nd Phase (M7 -M25)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Widely disseminate and communicate the project's concept and progress 2. Engage a wide variety of stakeholders 3. Establish synergies with several relevant projects 4. Built an active community to exchange knowledge and updates on the project and the sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project's logo - Project's website - Project's SMAs - Project's poster, leaflet, presentation and reporting templates, letterhead and banner - Project press release and publications

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Promote and accelerate the development of sustainable solutions for renewable energy and renewable fuel technologies; promote RES penetration and gender balance; promote an innovative multi-disciplinary approach on teaching and engaging with the sustainability of renewable energy 6. Present the EU MASTER AND VET; the industry-academia programme focused on hands-on training. 7. Raise awareness and spread knowledge through the Green Portal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project's Newsletter - Project's video - Project's internal events, workshops and webinars - Project's synergies with other relevant projects - Participation in external events and conferences - Green Portal
<p>3rd Phase (M26 -M36)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Effective dissemination of the project's outcomes 2. Facilitate the adoption of the project's outcomes 3. Dissemination of the project's policy recommendations 4. Engage the relevant stakeholders to ensure the exploitation of project results after the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project's logo - Project's website - Project's SMAs - Project's poster, leaflet, presentation and report templates, Letterheads - Project press release and publications - Project's Newsletter - Project's video - Project's internal events, workshops and webinars - Project's final dissemination event - Project's synergies with other relevant projects - Participation in external events and conferences - Green Portal
<p>4th Phase - Beyond the end of the project</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dissemination of project results 2. Post – project exploitation of the project's results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium partners' networks and means of communications

10. Conclusions

The updated version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan continues to be an important tool for publicising the SKILLBILL project and exploiting its results. This document continues to outline all dissemination and communication activities of the project that are necessary to maximise visibility through different communication channels and to address specific stakeholders. As the project activities are dynamically evolving, the dissemination and communication plan will be regularly updated to adapt it to the progress of SKILLBILL.

A final version of this document will be published in M36 which will also include any adjustments resulting from lessons learnt during the lifetime of the SKILLBILL project. As a result, adjustments will be made to the approach outlined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan to ensure that the promotion of the project maximises its impact with the targeted stakeholders and the wider European community.

ANNEXES

Annex 1. Dissemination and Communication Guidelines

Main Guidelines

1. Actively contribute to the dissemination of project results and key messages.
2. Use the wording “SKILLBILL” to refer to the project; do not use “SkillBill”.
3. For all your communications related to the project please include in your electronic signature the project logo, linked to the project's website.
4. Do not forget to include the EU logo and the disclaimer:

- a. When displayed with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.
 - b. You can download the needed EU emblem in the desired resolution following this link:
https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter/
5. If possible, follow the style guide concerning writing style, formatting options, numbers and currency, abbreviations and acronyms, captions, electronic cross-references, naming conventions, citation style.
6. Use Arial as font for documents generated with MS Office programmes and for web applications. The preferred spacing is 6 pt. before and after paragraph, whereas the preferred line spacing is single.
 - Make sure to use the logo colour scheme for documents to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of the project.
 - Whenever possible, use the logo letter type for promotional materials. If in doubt, check with White Research.
 - Always use the same style for references, both for in-text citations and in the bibliography/footnotes.
 - Be consistent in using currency references (for example, use EUR instead of € throughout).
 - Be consistent in the numbering format; comply with the British usage (e.g., 75,000,239.23), unless differently indicated.
 - If you abbreviate a word, use the correct abbreviation (for instance, “M” for million, not “mn”).
 - Make sure to introduce each abbreviation and acronym the first time you use it and create an abbreviation/acronym list at the beginning of the document.
 - Review the language and the coherence of the structure of the text you drafted.
7. Whenever possible, use the templates that will be provided to you, i.e., letterhead, presentation, publication. A leaflet and a poster will be prepared for you to use throughout the project. Other communication materials (e.g., infographics) will be prepared ad-hoc if needed.

8. **Always** inform White Research and AzzeroCO2 regarding every dissemination and communication activity that you plan to carry out (e.g., organisation of an event, articles on websites or magazines, participation in an external event, etc.). This will enable us to publicise it through the project's communication channels in a timely manner.
9. You will have to report in detail all the dissemination actions you undertook. Please see **Dissemination Reporting Template** for instructions.
10. Always report about meetings and events you organised and/or participated in. Please see **Internal Events Reporting Template** for an explanation on how to report about events.
11. Inform White Research and AzzeroCO2 about relevant events (e.g., conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) in which SKILLBILL partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. You have received an .xls file named "**External Conferences and Events**". All partners are kindly requested to fill in this specific .xls file, each time they identify an event relevant to the project and share it with White Research.
12. In compliance with GDPR requirements, always gather stakeholders' consent, when collecting, using and storing personal data during events/conferences. Please consider that pictures which make individuals identifiable are also considered personal data. Partners are responsible to gather participants' consent for the activities they undertake.

The above-mentioned points will be updated when necessary, in order to be in line with the project's requirements and progress.

The SKILLBILL report "**Dissemination and communication plan**" (First version due in M4; Update in M18) will include these guidelines and will also outline the overall project's dissemination strategy and plan.

Dissemination and monitoring tools

SKILLBILL Dissemination Reporting Template

This is an Excel file (online in the project's repository) that has to be updated on a monthly basis by all consortium partners. All the information required must be provided – the European Commission collects all these data from the Dissemination Manager. Therefore, for each activity please indicate:

- Date;
- Place;
- Short description;
- Type of activity;
- Online/physical;
- Title;
- If the activity is part of the project;
- Role and description of the organisation's involvement;
- Other project partners involved;
- Type of audience;
- Size of audience per type of stakeholder group;

- Countries addressed;
- Gender of audience;
- Type of material used and quantity (e.g. number of flyers distributed);
- Other partners or external organisation involved;
- Short description of action and dissemination activities;
- Other comments;
- Relevant contacts made (if consent was given).

SKILLBILL Events & Conferences Reporting Template

Internal events: the events that are planned to be held based on the GA and which are organized and coordinated by the consortium partners

The event report has to be sent after every event within 30 days to both White Research and AzeroCO2. It is a structured file that includes:

- Event data (title, date, venue, organisers, type and number of attendants, duration);
- Goals and relevance within the project;
- Organisation;
- Dissemination activities;
- Short minutes of the events (structure);
- Outcomes of the event;
- Evaluation;
- Appendixes (list of participants and scanned copy of the list signed by all participants– if possible, in compliance with the GDPR, agenda, photos, presentations).

SKILLBILL External Events & Conferences Reporting Template

External events: events that are not organized within the framework of SKILLBILL but are close to the project's theme. The participation of partners in these events is important to share knowledge and interact with key stakeholders

This is an Excel file that you can fill in each time you identify an external event (e.g. conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) relevant to SKILLBILL and in which SKILLBILL partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. Please share it with White Research and AzeroCO2.

Website and social media guidelines

Website

1. Collect photos and videos for all SKILLBILL activities and share them with White Research and AzeroCO2, to make them usable on the website and on the SKILLBILL SMAs.
2. Actively contribute (if possible, with one (1) news item per month per partner) to the news section of the website. Please send each news item to White Research and AzeroCO2. A news item can be anything, like a link to other similar projects/activities, an article about a new regulation, a notice regarding a new policy or initiative, an article about an event etc.

3. Inform White Research regarding every event you organise or take part to for the purposes of the project (e.g., conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) and provide White Research and AzeroCO₂ with a link to the event, so that it can be posted online in the dedicated section of the website.
4. Inform White Research about news articles (e.g., newspaper article, blogpost, TV interview etc.) mentioning your pilot area or the SKILLBILL project and provide WR with a link/scan for giving it more visibility online. All provided material should be written in English.

Social Media Accounts

1. Connect with all SKILLBILL SMAs (i.e. Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube) and use them accordingly: monitor announcements and posts, comment, like and retweet.
2. Do make your own posts on your own SMAs to foster discussion and maintain project's accounts' activity.
3. If you would like White Research to publish a post on one or more of the SMAs (e.g., promote an event that is coming up in your city, announce the achievement of a milestone, etc.), please share the post using the dedicated Excel file on SKILLBILL Dropbox (Dropbox (SkillBill)\WP6\T6.1\4_Dissemination & Communication Guidelines-Reporting Templates).
4. Promote the SKILLBILL SMAs within your network of contacts.
5. Inform White Research about any relevant profiles (e.g. sister projects) you may detect during the project, so that we can expand our network on SMAs.
6. If you create a short video, make any edits necessary in order to improve the project's identity (add the project's name, logo, EU emblem and the official Horizon EUROPE disclaimer). White Research is then accountable for uploading the video on YouTube.

The above-mentioned points will be updated, when necessary, to be in line with the project's requirements and progress.

Annex 2: Dissemination Reporting Template

The form below has been designed to help you keep track of any kind of awareness and dissemination activities. Just to remind you, dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, meetings, workshops, interviews, press releases, publications, e-mails, presentations, informal discussions, seminars, etc. Please, complete any relevant parts of the form below each time you perform a dissemination activity either this is small or large.

Important: Specify the type of activity as well as the type of the audience(s) addressed using the categories provided in the drop-down menu.

No. of Action	Partner	Other partners involved	Basic Info			Material used	Other	
			Date of activity	Place of activity	Short description of the action	Quantity of project material used (no. of copies distributed per type of project material)	Other comments (IF RELEVANT)	Significant contacts made IF RELEVANT (name, position, organisation; add also address, tel, e-mail)
<i>example#1</i>	WR	Q-PLAN	<i>example 1/11/2022</i>	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Paper	2	N/A	N/A
<i>example#1</i>						50		
1	PC		15/09/2022	https://portal	Info about the project on the			
2	PC		15/09/2022	https://www.linkedin.com/p	Social media post on KoM	138 impressions		
3	PC		21/11/2022	https://www.linkedin.com/p	Social media post about KoM	38 reach		
4	PC		21/11/2022	https://www.facebook.com/	Social media post about KoM	649 impressions		
5	PC		12/1/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/p	Social media post about	248 impressions		
6	PC		12/1/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/p	Social media repost	270 impressions		
7	PC		8/2/2023	(6) PEDAL Consulting (@PED)	SM in Slovak about 2nd	87 impressions		
8	PC		8/2/2023	(8) Post Feed LinkedIn	SM in Slovak about 2nd	221 impressions		
9	PC		8/2/2023	https://www.facebook.com/	SM in Slovak about 2nd	n/a		
13	METROPOLIA		22-23/5/2023	Brussels, Belgium	Poster on SkillBill project			
14	METROPOLIA		1/6/2023	Amsterdam, Netherlands	Poster presentation on			
15	METROPOLIA		8/6/2023	Bucharest, Romania	Break-Out Session			

Readme M1-M6 M7-M12 M13-M18 M19-M24 M25-M30 M31-M36 Lists

D6.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan (updated version), 29/02/2024

The form below has been designed to help you keep track of any kind of awareness and dissemination activities. Just to remind you, dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, meetings, workshops, interviews, press releases, publications, e-mails, presentations, informal discussions, seminars, etc. Please, complete any relevant parts of the form below each time you perform a dissemination activity either this is small or large.

Important: Specify the type of activity as well as the type of the audience(s) addressed using the categories provided in the drop-down menu.

		Basic Info			Activity details		Material used	Other	
No. of Action	Partner	Date of activity	Place of activity	Short description of the action	Type of activity (Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)	Was the activity online?	Quantity of project material used (no. of copies distributed per type of project material)	Other comments (IF RELEVANT)	Significant contacts made IF RELEVANT (name, position, organisation; add also address, tel, e-mail)
1	PC	31/03/2023	https://twitter.com/PEDALconsulting/status/1641876600462655488	Energy Academy	Social Media	Online	368 impressions		
2	PC	31/03/2023	https://www.facebook.com/pedalconsulting/posts/pfbid02BQ5F38HZJP8KD6aJK1e8BwMaWg7JDF9vHTmU5QyX7mo29X4h53DLcybBb6ParJuSl	Energy Academy	Social Media	Online	n/a		
3	PC	12/4/2023	https://www.linkedin.com	Green portal promo -	Social Media	Online	193 impressions		
4	PC	12/4/2023	https://www.facebook.com	Green portal promo -	Social Media	Online	n/a		
5	PC	12/4/2023	https://twitter.com/PEDAL	Green portal promo -	Social Media	Online	35 impressions		
6	PC	29/05/2023	https://www.linkedin.com	SKILLBILL CCW - SK	Social Media	Online	96 impressions		
7	PC	14/06/2023	https://www.linkedin.com	The future of renewable	Social Media	Online	219 impressions		
8	PC	14/06/2023	https://www.facebook.com	The future of renewable	Social Media	Online	47 reach		
9	PC	14/06/2023	https://twitter.com/PEDAL	The future of renewable	Social Media	Online	34 impressions		
10	PC	12/07/2023	Zaujímajú vás,	Are you interested in	Social Media	Online	57 reach		
11	PC	12/07/2023	https://twitter.com/PEDAL	Are you interested in	Social Media	Online	15 impressions		
12	PC	12/07/2023	https://www.instagram.com	Are you interested in	Social Media	Online	n/a		
13	PC	12/07/2023	https://www.instagram.com	Are you interested in	Social Media	Online	n/a		
14	PC	24/07/2023	https://www.linkedin.com	SKILLBILL repost	Social Media	Online	95 impressions		
15	PC	24/07/2023	(3) POSILNENIE	SKILLBILL repost	Social Media	Online	26 reach		
16	PC	24/07/2023	https://twitter.com/PEDAL	SKILLBILL repost	Social Media	Online	27 impressions		
17	PC	24/07/2023	https://www.instagram.com	SKILLBILL repost	Social Media	Online	n/a		
18	PC	07/08/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/pedal-consulting-platform-educate-renewable-activity-7094249070646456320-Z-07?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_des	SKILLBILL Green portal (in Slovak Language)	Social Media	Online	15 impressions		

Readme M1-M6 M7-M12 M13-M18 M19-M24 M25-M30 M31-M36 Lists (+)

Annex 3: SKILLBILL Events & Conferences Reporting Template

The following template is *completed based on T2.2. digital co-creation workshop*

Event's Aggregate Data

Time (CET)	Topic
Welcome	
11:00 – 11:05	Start of Workshop – Welcome
11:05 – 11:15	Tour de la table
11.15 – 11.25	Introduction to SKILLBILL Project – Presentation of the Topic
11:25 – 11:30	Icebreaker – Online tools explanation
Session 1: Operation of the Working Groups	
11:30 – 11:50	Working Groups Insights and Operational Model
11:50 – 12:00	Feedback on operational model by the participants - Discussion
12:00 – 12:15	Break
Session 2: Thematic Focus Co-creation	
12:15 – 12:30	Timeline and expected outcomes by the working groups
12:30 – 13:30	Co-creation session on the topics of discussion of each working group
13:30 – 13:55	Presentation of results – Discussion – Wrap up
Meeting Conclusion	
13:55 – 14:00	Highlights – Closing

Stakeholders reached

What type of stakeholders were engaged?

- Define the type(s) of stakeholders reached (policy, SMEs, general public etc.)
- How many people attended?

A diverse group of 32 participants, including external stakeholders, experts on renewable energy across the quadruple helix, advisory board members, and consortium partners

Event's goals, objectives and relevance with SKILLBILL

What were the key objectives of this event/activity? (e.g. to gather ideas, gather data, find new stakeholders, etc). How was the event relevant to SKILLBILL? To what extent?

1. Sustainable and Renewable Electricity & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential
2. Sustainable Mobility & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential
3. Sustainable and Renewable Heat & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential
4. Sustainable and Renewable Fuels & Skills Gap impacting its full deployment potential

Organisation of the event

In case of organizing a project's event. **For participation in external events do not complete this section.**

How was the event/activity organized?

- What steps were taken to set up the activity/event?
- What was the location of the event and why was this area selected?

Identification of the co-creation workshop participants.

Doodle for setting up the date

Task Leader (QPLAN) shared an invitation together with workshop's agenda for the participants to mark their calendars

A link to the digital co-creation workshop was also shared by the organizer

Dissemination activities

How was the event/activity promoted? Was project material used for promotion? If not, why?

The digital co-creation workshops was disseminated before and after its completion using SKILLBILL's website and social media accounts.

Structure of the event (short minutes)

Description of the event's sessions.

- What did the event/activity consist of?
- What tools were used? Why were these selected?

For participation in external events, please report what you did at the event.

CCW utilized the Miro voting tool to determine the most prominent topics for discussion. Each proposal was displayed on a digital canvas within Miro, and participants were given the opportunity to cast their votes for the topics they found most compelling and relevant to the WGs' objectives. As the votes were tallied, the most prominent topics emerged, as presented in the following table, , guiding the WGs in setting their agendas for the upcoming meetings. The democratic nature of the voting process ensured that the final selection of topics truly represented the interests and aspirations of the participants, fostering a sense of ownership.

Outcomes of the event

What information or data was gathered as part of this activity? (a brief summary of the information/data gathered is sufficient)

What ideas were generated? (brief explanations are sufficient)

The following topics were identified as the most prominent for discussion.

- ✓ Solutions for driving the development and adoption of sustainable renewable energy and fuels techs.
- ✓ Directions for regulatory shifts that help share a favourable environment for sustainable renewable energy and fuels tech diffusion.
- ✓ Guidelines for education / training programs to facilitate skilling, reskilling and upskilling.
- ✓ Identification of new jobs and skills required for the shaping of the next generation of sustainable renewable energy and fuels technologies

Evaluation of the event

What are the main impressions and observations that you made?

- Were there any challenges with this event/activity?
- What were the key successes of this activity?
- If re-deploying this event/activity how will/would you do it differently?

The digital co-creation workshop played a pivotal role in evaluating the success and effectiveness of the renewable energy initiatives, empowering the WGs to make informed decisions and drive positive change in the energy sector.

ANNEX: Attachments

- The list of participants (if consent to store and share data was given)
- A scanned copy of the list of participants signed by each participant (if possible)
- The agenda of the event
- Photos (**please make sure to have the consent of participants to use them**)
- Presentations (if applicable)
- Copies of materials used to promote the event (e.g., links to press releases, videos, posts, leaflets etc.)

Annex 4: SKILLBILL External Events & Conferences Reporting Template

No.	Event's name	Thematic Focus	Abbreviation	Date	Location	Registration fees	Deadline for submission	Website	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission, ...)	Added by (Partner)
example	Example: 19th European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production – Circular Europe for Sustainability: Design, Production and Consumption	Circular economy, sustainable production	ERSCP 2019	15-18 October 2019	Barcelona	EUR 225-550	Closed (18/02/2019)	https://erscp2019.eu	N/A	WR
1	European Sustainable Energy Week 2023	Career opportunities in the energy transition: the skills you need for the green economy	EUSEW 2023	20-22	22	none	online	https://energy.ec.europa.eu/events/european-sustainable-energy-week-2023-2023-06-20_en	no	AzZeroCO2
2	FemPower Summer School 2023	Summer School		2 Sep. 2023	Thessaloniki		live	https://fempower.ee.auth.gr/summer-school/	SKILLBILL project overall presentation	WR
3	9th SBA Professional Conference - The Future of Slovak Biogas 2023	Conference		19-20 October 2023	Martin	EUR 249-750 (promotional stand + other benefits incl.)	onset	http://www.sba.sk/actualitu/pozyvame-vas-na-9-rocnik-odbornej-konferencie-sba-buducnost-slovenskeho-bioplynu-2023/	SKILLBILL project overall presentation	PC
4	Final conference of RESTART project	Final conference		25-Oct-23	Bratislava	none	online registration form		none	PC
5	Smart City Expo	Exhibition		7-9 Nov. 2023	Barcelona			https://www.smartcityexpo.com/the-event/		PC

Figure 44. SKILLBILL's External Events & Conferences Reporting Template

The project

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers. The basic idea underlying the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and qualitatively appropriate both to train the adequate number of workers and to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES besides their initial level of education and their working position. It's important, beside the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, to have awareness modules for unspecific public in order to fight against ignorance, fake news, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills. Thus, SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels to analyse and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language; create several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice; develop and implement innovative learning method; and evaluate the work performed.

Coordinator: **AZZERO CO2 SRL (AzzeroCO2)**

PARTNER	SHORT NAME	
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